

THE
SELENOPIDAE
OF
SOUTH AFRICA

Compiled by: A.S. Dippenaar-Schoeman, C.R. Haddad, S.H. Foord & L.N. Lotz

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ABSTRACT

The family Selenopidae is known from nine genera and 260 species (World Spider Catalog 2020). They are well represented in the Afrotropical Region and from South Africa two genera and 71 species are known. Lawrence (1940) alone described 37 species in one paper. The genus *Anyphops* was erected by Benoit (1968) for several species previously listed in the *Selenops*. From South Africa 58 *Anyphops* species are known. Thirteen species are listed in *Selenops* with some of the revisional work done by Corronca (2002, 2005). Of the 71 species 41 are known only from the female and 10 from the male. Of the total number of species 47 (66%) are listed as Least Concern and 23 (32%) are Data Deficient. Only one species, *Anyphops kraussi* (Pocock, 1898), a Western Cape endemic, is listed as Rare. Fifty-two species (73%) are South African endemics, 8 are African endemics and 10 are southern African endemics with only one, *Selenops radiatus* Latreille, 1819, with a wider than Africa distribution. In an unpublished report (Corronca) another 20 species have been identified as possibly new.

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* Species from South Africa not listed in the World Spider Catalog (2020)

FAMILY SELENOPIDAE Simon, 1897

The family Selenopidae is known from nine genera and 260 species (World Spider Catalog 2020). They are well represented in the Afrotropical Region and from South Africa two genera and 71 species are known.

COMMON NAMES: Flatties or Wall Spiders.

MORPHOLOGY: Body size: 6-23 mm. Colour: body cream to grey, mottled with black, brown and grey, legs sometimes banded. Carapace flattened and sub circular; eyes: 8 in 2 rows (6:2) with the anterior row containing 6 eyes wide near edge of carapace; posterior row with 2 fairly large eyes, one on each side. Abdomen flattened; round to oval in shape and densely clothed with setae. Legs: 2 claws with claw tufts and scopula; legs directed sideways with anterior legs provided with strong, paired setae on tibiae and metatarsi I and II. Markings on body and legs variable and identification from photographs difficult.

LIFESTYLE: Free-running plant and ground dwellers. With their very flattened bodies they are able to move into narrow crevices. They dart with astonishing speed sideways for cover when disturbed. With their mottled bodies they blend in with their surroundings whether on the soil surface, rocks or tree trunks. They are commonly found in agro-ecosystems especially in orchards like avocado and macadamia. Selenopids are among the most common spiders encountered in houses in Southern Africa, living on the walls. They are attracted by light in the evening and prey on the insects that gather around the light. When disturbed they disappear under wall hangings or in crevices. Their disc-shaped, satin smooth egg cocoons are attached to the under surface of stones and in houses are easily seen when attached to dark wooden beams. Local people use it as a vibrating element in music instruments. They have a very wide habitat range and have been collected from all the different biomes. They are synantropic and commonly found in houses on the walls.

TAXONOMY: The African genera and species have been studied by Lawrence (1940), Benoit(1968) and Corronca (2000, 2002, 2005).

Anyphops sp. eye pattern

Selenops sp. eye pattern

The following quick key may be used for distinguishing the main groups of species found in the South African region (after Lawrence 1940)

1. Metatarsi of anterior legs with 2 pairs of inferior spines, tibiae with 3 pairs of inferior spines**SELENOPS**
2. Metatarsi of anterior legs with 3 pairs of inferior spines, tibiae with 4-7 pairs of inferior spines**ANYPHOPS**

Quick key to *Anyphops* spp.

1. Anterior tibiae with 4 pairs of inferior spines

- A. lawrencei* FS, KZN
- A. lycosiformis* KZN
- A. lucia* KZN
- A. mumai* EC
- A. natalensis* KZN
- A. ngome* KZN
- A. parvulus* EC, WC

2. Anterior tibiae with 5 pairs of inferior spines

- A. alticola* KZN, MP
- A. atomarius* EC, WC
- A. barnardi* G, NC
- A. bechuanicus* KZN, NW
- A. broomi* FS, NC, WC
- A. caledonicus* WC
- A. civicus* EC, FS, KZN
- A. helenae* WC
- A. hessei* NC, WC, FS
- A. hewitti* EC, MP
- A. immaculatus* [5 PROV]
- A. karrooicus* EC, NC, FS
- A. lawrencei* FS, G, KZN
- A. lesserti* WC
- A. lignicola* KZN, MP
- A. longipedatus* G, NW, KZN
- A. maculosus* EC, WC, NC
- A. minor* KZN, WC
- A. namaquensis* NC, WC

- A. narcissi* M, KZN
- A. phallus* KZN
- A. pococki* KZN, MP, NW
- A. purcelli* EC, WC
- A. schoenland* EC
- A. thornei* WC

3. Anterior tibiae with 6 pairs of inferior spines

- A. amatolae* EC
- A. barbertonensis* [6 PROV]
- A. braunsi* MP, EC
- A. capensis* EC, WC
- A. dubiosus* KZN
- A. fitzsimonsi* G, MP, NW
- A. gilli* EC, WC, KZN
- A. kraussi* WC
- A. leleupi* L, MP
- A. lochiel* L, MP
- A. montanus* WC
- A. regalis* WC
- A. reservatus* L, KZN
- A. sexspinatus* NC
- A. stauntoni* EC, G, KZN
- A. stridulans* NC
- A. transvaalicus* MP
- A. tuckeri* [6 PROV.]

4. Anterior tibiae with 7 pairs of inferior spines

- A. basutus* EC, KZN
- A. decoratus* [4 PROV]
- A. marshalli* EC, WC, KZN
- A. rubicundus* L, M, WC
- A. septemspinatus* L, KZN
- A. silvicollellus* L
- A. spenceri* EC, KZN, L
- A. whiteae* EC, KZN
- A. tugelana* KZN

GENUS *ANYPHOPS* Benoit, 1968

The genus *Anyphops* was erected by Benoit (1968) for several species previously listed in the *Selenops*. From South Africa 58 species are known.

COMMON NAME: Anyphops Flatties or Wall Spiders.

TYPE SPECIES: *Anyphops atomarius* (Simon, 1887)

MORPHOLOGY: Small to large (6-23 mm) spiders. *Anyphops* differs from other selenopid genera in the arrangement of the eyes, the number of ventral spines on tibiae I – II, the shape of the median apophysis of the male palp, the general structure of the female epigynum and the leg formulae. Carapace flattened; subcircular; usually brown to reddish brown, with lateral dark bands or spots; chelicerae brown to orange, normally with black or grey bands; labium and sternum usually paler in colour; anterior median eyes and posterior median eyes are in a strongly recurved line; posterior median eyes larger than anterior median eyes; posterior lateral eyes the largest, anterior lateral eyes the smallest. Abdomen flattened, round to oval; clothed in dense setae; normally grey or yellowish with brown or black dorsal defined patterns; venter yellowish, without markings. Leg two claws with claw tufts and scopulae; laterigrade; anterior legs provided with strong, four to seven pairs of ventral spines on tibiae and metatarsi I and II; tarsal claws smooth; formulae normally 4321. Male palp with a retrolateral tibial apophysis with two branches similar in size or the dorsal longer than the ventral. Female epigynum with a middle field reduced or well developed, represented by a depression or a septum, the lateral lobes of the epigynum well distinguished or not and, in very few cases, with slight secondary epigyneal pockets.

LIFESTYLE: They are free-living, agile spiders found on rocks, walls and tree trunks. With their very flattened bodies they are able to move into narrow crevices. Different species frequently occur sympatrically but occupy different microhabitats. The egg sac is round, flat, and papery that are attached to stones or bark (Croeser 1979) .

TAXONOMY: The genus was studied by Lawrence (1940), Benoit (1968) and Corronca (2000, 2002, 2005).

Anyphops lawrencei egg sac from the Waterberg Photo Lee Guttiger

Emerging spiderlings from egg sac Photo Cambry

Anyphops alticola (Lawrence, 1940)

COMMON NAME: Ingwavuma Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A KwaZulu-Natal endemic described by Lawrence (1940) as *Selenops alticolus* from Ingwavuma. The species is presently known from two provinces (EOO=23 370 km²; AOO=12 km²; 27-928 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the female and to determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal*: Ingwavuma (-27.12, 32.01); Richards Bay (15 km N) (28.78, 32.1). *Mpumalanga*: Groblersdal (-25.16, 29.39).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal spiders. This species was sampled from the soil surface in forested and grassland areas in the Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011). One specimen was also sampled from a house in Richards Bay.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are unknown. Some more sampling is needed to collect the female and to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Benoit (1968). Known only from the male. Carapace light brown with some darker patches along the lateral margins, eyes surrounded by black; mandibles reddish brown, darker than carapace, the inner half of their anterior surfaces blackish brown; abdomen brown, variegated with some minute light dots and blackish markings; legs with very weak bands and spots, the strongest being a longitudinal bar near the base of the infero-anterior surface of femur I and II. Anterior tibiae with 5 pairs of rather weak inferior spines, no lateral or superior spines; anterior metatarsi with 3 pairs of inferior spines, no lateral spines. Size TL 6-8 mm (Lawrence 1940).

Anyphops alticola imm male Photo Peter Webb

After Lawrence (1940)

Anyphops amatolae (Lawrence, 1940)

COMMON NAME: Hogsback Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An Eastern Cape endemic described by Lawrence (1940) as *Selenops amatolae* from Hogsback (EOO=4 km²; AOO=4 km²; 1307 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure as the type specimen was sampled in 1933. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape*: Hogsback (-32.59, 26.92)

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground dwellers. Sampled from the Forest Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are unknown. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range and to collect the male.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Corronca (2000). Known from both sexes. Carapace finely bordered with black, dark brown with long blackish radiations from the thoracic stria, the latter appearing as a wedge-shaped dark marking pointed posteriorly; mandibles similar in colour to carapace; abdomen above rubbed; femora and tibiae of anterior legs with broad brown bands. Tibia I and II with 6 pairs of strong and very long spines (the longest about a third the length of tibia I), metatarsus I and II with 3 pairs of even longer spines (the longest about half the length of metatarsus I). Size TL 15 mm (Lawrence 1940).

After Lawrence (1940)

After Corronca (unpublished) abdomen and epigyne

Anypops atomarius (Simon, 1887)

COMMON NAME: Eastern Cape Anypops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South Africa endemic described as Simon (1887) as *Selenops atomarius* from Port Elizabeth. The species has been sampled from two provinces (EOO=31 270 km²; AOO=20 km²; 7-552 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographic range, the species is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Grahamstown (-33.3, 26.52); Port Elizabeth (-33.95, 25.61); 2 km N. Steytlerville Karoo Hotel (-33.32, 24.34); Alicedale (-33.31, 26.08). **Western Cape:** Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground dwellers. Sampled from the Fynbos and Thicket biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: The species was revised by Benoit (1968). Known from both sexes. Legs with distinct bands. Anterior tibiae with 5 inferior pairs of spines, II with 1 posterior lateral spine in addition, anterior metatarsi with 3 inferior pairs of spines. Size TL 8 mm (Lawrence 1940).

A. atomarius.female from Cape Town Photo Heather Hodgson

After Corronca (unpublished) abdomen, epigyne and palp

Anyphops barbertonensis (Lawrence, 1940)

COMMON NAME: Barberton Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described as Lawrence (1940) as *Selenops barbertonensis* from Barberton in Mpumalanga. In South Africa known from six provinces (EOO=403 290 km²; AOO=72 km²; 1-1730 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Somalia (erroneous listing in WSC 2020), Swaziland and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Jeffreys Bay (-34.06, 24.91); Mkhambathi Nature Reserve (-31.32, 29.97). **Free State:** Wyndford Guest Farm Fouriesburg (-28.7, 28.24). **Gauteng:** Kliprivierberg (-26.27, 28.08); Klipriviersberg Nature Reserve Site 3 (-26.3075, 28.0147); Klipriviersberg Nature Reserve Site 4 (-26.2908, 28.0789); Irene (-25.868, 28.218). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Greytown (-29.05, 30.6); Ndumo Game Reserve, Crocodile Farm (-26.87, 32.24); Sungulwane Game Reserve (-28.87, 31.18); Wakefield Farm (-29.473, 29.893). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.038, 29.442). **Mpumalanga:** Barberton (-25.79, 31.04); Barberton between Badplaas and Barberton (-25.79, 31.04); Lowveld National Botanical Gardens (-25.47, 31); Mariepskop (-24.58, 30.87).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground dwellers that have been sampled with pitfall traps and from under rocks in the Fynbos, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. Protected in the Mkhambathi Nature Reserve, Klipriviersberg Nature Reserve, Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad et al. 2006), Sungulwane Game Reserve, Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2019) and Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (Muelelwa et al. 2011).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Benoit (1968). Species known from only the female. Carapace light brown with spots and dashes of brown, thoracic radiations faint, thoracic striae and sides of cephalic area defined by brown stripes, cephalic area bisected by a faint median stripe, which at half-way gives off a branch to each posterior median eye; mandibles light brown, their inner apices darkened; abdomen light brown, finely speckled with some larger indistinct bars and spots. Tibia I and II with 6, metatarsus I and II with 3 pairs of inferior spines. Size TL 12.2 mm (Lawrence 1940).

Anyphops barbertonensis from Irene Photo Peter Webb

Anyphops barnardi (Lawrence, 1940)

COMMON NAME: Barnard's Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described by Lawrence (1940) as *Selenops barnardi* from Pokwani Zimbabwe. In South Africa known from two provinces (EOO=12 713 km²; AOO=20 km²; 1069-1457 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Zimbabwe, Mozambique and South Africa (new record).

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Northern Cape:** Rooipoort Nature Reserve (-28.671, 24.213). **Gauteng:** Pretoria(-25.74, 28.19); Meyerspark (-25.7395, 28.3138); Rietvleidam Nature Reserve (-25.85, 28.16).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground dwellers. They have been sampled with pitfall traps and from under rocks in the Savanna and Grassland biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. Protected in the Rooipoort Nature Reserve and Rietvleidam Nature Reserve. More sampling needed to collect the male.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Last revised by Benoit (1968). Known from only the female. Carapace fairly dark reddish brown, cephalic a little darker than thoracic portion, ocular area black, radiations from the thoracic stria not strongly marked, a number of submarginal spots subjoined to form a wavy band; mandibles a little darker than cephalic area; abdomen above blackish brown, with some ill-defined symmetrical markings; legs with well-defined and fairly strong bands. Tibia I and II with 5, metatarsus I and II with 3 pairs of inferior spines. Size TL: 30.3 mm (Lawrence 1940).

After Lawrence (1940)

Epigyne Photo ASD

Anyphops barnardi from Rooipoort Nature Reserve Photo ASD

Anyphops basutus (Pocock, 1901)

COMMON NAME: Lesotho Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described by Pocock (1901) from Lesotho as *Selenops basutus*. In South Africa sampled from two provinces (EOO= 22 650 km²; AOO=12 km²; 375-169 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex, it has a wide geographical range and is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Lesotho, South Africa (new record).

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Mzimhlava river mouth. Transkei coast Lusikisiki District (-31.37, 29.57). *KwaZulu-Natal:* Vernon Crookes Nature Reserve (-30.27, 30.57).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground dwellers. The species has been sampled from Forest and Indian Ocean Coastal Belt.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species, it is protected in the Vernon Crookes Nature Reserve. More sampling needed to determine the range

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Last revised by Benoit (1968). Known only from the female. Resemble *A. atomarius* and *A. spenceri* in having 7 pairs of tibial spines on leg I and II. Size TL 18 mm (Pocock 1901).

After Corronca (unpublished) abdomen, epigyne and palp

Anyphops basutus from KZN Photo Peter Webb

Anyphops bechuanicus (Lawrence, 1940)

COMMON NAME: Vryburg Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South Africa endemic described by Lawrence (1940) from Vryburg in the North West as *Selenops bechuanicus*. The species have been sampled from two provinces (EOO<1000 km²; AOO=8 km²; 71-1218 m a.s.l.). The species is under sampled and some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa. (wrongly listed as from Botswana).

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal:* Uvongo (-30.82,30.39). *North West:* Vryburg (-26.95, 24.73).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground dwellers sampled from the Savanna (Foord et al. 2011) and Indian Ocean Coastal Belt biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are unknown. But the species is under sampled and some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes. Carapace yellow-brown, narrowly bordered with black and variegated with symmetrical brown markings, an oval patch on each side of the thoracic striae; mouthparts light yellow-brown, a narrow inner and outer dark stripe on their anterior surfaces; abdomen yellow-brown with indistinct symmetrical markings; legs with distinct dark bands, those of the femora mottled and irregular, those of the tibiae clearly defined. Tibia I and II with 5, metatarsus I and II with 3 pairs of inferior spines. Size TL: 9.5 mm (Lawrence 1940).

After Lawrence (1940)

Anyphops bechuanicus Photo Peter Webb

Anyphops braunsi (Lawrence, 1940)

COMMON NAME: Willowmore Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Lawrence (1940) from Willowmore in the Eastern Cape as *Selenops braunsi*. The species is known from two provinces (EOO=72 953 km²; AOO=16 km²; 62-1050 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Baviaanskloof Nature Reserve (-33.76, 24.81); Willowmore (-33.3, 23.5); Van Stadens Pass (-33.15, 25.03). *Mpumalanga:* Bergvliet Forest Station (-25.1, 30.78); Delmas (-26.14, 28.68).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground dwellers sampled from the Forest, Savanna (Foord et al. 2011) and Thicket biomes. Different species frequently occur sympatrically but occupy different microhabitats. Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman (1988) collected the species on the ground in a pine plantation at Sabie, South Africa.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are unknown. It is protected in the Baviaanskloof Nature Reserve and Bergvliet Forest Station (Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman 1988).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Last revised by Benoit (1968). Known from only the female. Carapace light reddish brown, thoracic striae well defined, with some fine lines radiating from it, a line from the striae bisecting the cephalic area and bifurcating behind the anterior median eyes; mandibles a little darker than carapace; abdomen rubbed, yellow above but with some darker spots and blotches above the spinners; legs with the dark bands. Size TL 12 mm. Tibia I and II with 6, metatarsus I and II with 3 pairs of inferior spines (Lawrence 1940).

After Lawrence (1940)

Anyphops braunsi from Delmas Photo Peter Webb

Epigyne and abdomen after Corronca (unpublished)

Anyphops broomi (Pocock, 1900)

COMMON NAME: Garies Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Pocock (1900) from Garies in the Northern Cape as *Selenops broomi*. The species is known from three provinces (EOO=438 800 km²; AOO=32 km²; 27-1645 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range, the species is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Free States: Fouriesburg Wyndford Guest Farm (-28.7, 28.24). **Northern Cape:** Garies (-30.56, 17.97); Kleinsee (-29.67, 17.07); Steinkopf, Little Namaqualand ("Petit" Namaqualand) (-29.25, 17.73); Richtersveld National Park (-28.25, 17.17); Sendelingsdrif (-26.96, 26.26); Hay Dist. Farm Lockshoek 567 (-28.75, 23.20). **Western Cape:** Klaarstroom (-33.33, 22.54).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground dwellers from Grassland, Desert and Succulent Karoo biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. It is protected in the Richtersveld National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes. Carapace yellow brown, thoracic striae black and strongly defined, continued on to the cephalic portion as a very fine black line, radiations from thoracic striae long, fine, but distinct; abdomen light brown, with some short (longitudinal) black bars and spots, a wavy transverse blackish band above the spinners; legs with dark bands, those on the femora poorly defined, especially the posterior ones, those of the tibia well defined. Colour of male much lighter than in female. Anterior tibiae with 5, anterior metatarsi with 3 pairs of inferior spines. Size TL female 14-15 mm, male 13-14 mm (Lawrence 1940).

Anyphops broomi from Wyndford Farm Photo Peter Webb

After Lawrence (1940)

Anyphops caledonicus (Lawrence, 1940)

COMMON NAME: Caledon Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described (<100 km²; AOO=4 km²; 237m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Therefore listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape:* Caledon (-34.24, 19.43); Bontebok National Park (-34.07, 20.45).

LIFESTYLE: Little is known about their behaviour. Sampled from the Fynbos Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Treats to the species are unknown. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. It is protected in the Bontebok National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from female. Carapace light yellow-brown with a Y-shaped darker marking formed by the thoracic striae and posterior boundaries of the cephalic area, a few small dark spots halfway between the striae and lateral margins; abdomen above with 3 pairs of short curved blackish bars; well-defined brown bands on femora and tibiae of all legs. Tibia I and II with 5, metatarsus I and II with 3 pairs of inferior spines. Size TL female 7-8 mm (Lawrence 1940).

After Lawrence (1940)

A. caledonicus from Bontebok NP Photo Elton le Roux

Anyphops capensis (Lawrence, 1940)

COMMON NAME: Cape Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South Africa endemic described by Lawrence (1940) from Cape Town as *Selenops capensis*. The species has been sampled from two provinces (EOO=121 833 km²; AOO=56 km²; 7-1513 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range, the species is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Eastern Cape: Mountain Zebra National Park (-32.24, 25.43). **Western Cape:** Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42); Clifton, Cape Peninsula (-33.93, 18.38); De Hoop Nature Reserve, Potberg (-34.45, 20.44); Gordon's Bay, Steenbras River (-34.16, 18.87); Hermanus (-34.4, 19.25); Kalkbaai (-34.19, 18.42); Kirstenbosch National Botanical Garden (-33.99, 18.43); Matroosberg (-33.42, 19.84); Sir Lowry's Pass (-34.13, 18.94); Table Mountain National Park (-33.82, 18.48); Table Mountain National Park Newlands Forest (-33.91, 18.42); Tradouw Pass Swellendam 2000-4000ft (-33.95, 20.7); Grootfontein Vredendal 105 (-31.66, 18.49); Lemoenkop Fernkloof Nature Reserve Hermanus (-34.61, 19.34).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal spiders sampled from the Fynbos Biome. In the De Hoop Nature Reserve they were sampled from under bark in eucalyptus plantation and fynbos. Also found in houses on walls.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. Protected in the Mountain Zebra National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 1988), De Hoop Nature Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2009) and Table Mountain National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes. Carapace yellow-brown with darker radii from the thoracic striae, cephalic portion a little darker than thoracic portion; abdomen above yellow-brown with small scattered blackish dots, darker towards the posterior apex, especially at the sides and just above the spinners; the dark dots on the posterior portion are characteristic. Legs not strongly banded, tibiae with two light and two dark bands. Anterior tibiae with 6 pairs of inferior spines. Size TL female 13-14 mm, male 12-13 mm (Lawrence 1940).

Anyphops capensis male from De Hoop Photo Charles Haddad

Genitalia and abdomen after Corronca (unpublished)

After Lawrence (1940)

Anyphops civicus (Lawrence, 1940)

COMMON NAME: Burgersdorp Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Lawrence (1940) from Burgersdorp in the Eastern Cape as *Selenops civicus*. The species is known from a few localities in three provinces (EOO=58 955 km²; AOO=16 km²; 291-1417 m a.s.l.). It has a wide geographical range and is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Burgersdorp (-30.99, 26.32); Waterford (-33.07, 25.02). **Free State:** Smithfield (-30.21, 26.53); **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ngome State Forest (-27.78, 31.45); Illovo beach (-30.12, 30.85).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal spiders sampled from the Grassland, Nama Karoo and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. Protected in the Ngome State Forest (Van der Merwe et al. 1996).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes. The markings of the carapace forming a fairly well-defined crenulated submarginal band, sides with a narrow blackish margin and between this and the submarginal band some blackish-brown spots; foveal radiations indistinct, legs with markings as in *A. karrooicus*; abdomen above with some indistinct brown markings on the posterior half, including some indistinct A-shaped markings. Anterior tibiae with 5 pairs of inferior spines. Size TL 7-12.5 mm (Lawrence 1940) .

After Lawrence (1940)

Anyphops civicus from Illovo Photo Peter Webb

Anypops decoratus (Lawrence, 1940)

COMMON NAME: Zululand Anypops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described Lawrence (1940) from Ingwavuma as *Selenops decoratus*. The species is sampled from four provinces (EOO=144 159 km²; AOO=36 km²; 29-1245 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range, the species is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Transkei coast Mzimhlava river mouth (-31.37, 29.58). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ingwavuma (-27.12, 32.01); Richards Bay (15 km N) (-28.78, 32.1); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Pinetown (-29.81, 30.85); uMkhuze Game Reserve (-27.609, 32.227); Kloof (-29.78, 30.83). **Limpopo:** Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (-24.17, 30.25). **Mpumalanga:** Kalkfontein Farm Groblersdal (-25.25, 29.48); Sabie Bergvliet State Forest (-25.10, 30.78).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal spiders sampled from the Forest, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species and protected in three reserves: Tembe Elephant Park (Haddad et al. (2009), uMkhuze Game Reserve and Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2016).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes. Carapace brown, narrowly margined with black, decorated with spots and short bars of black, including a row of black spots along the lateral margin, and a large one on each side of the stria along the posterior margin; mandibles brown, their inner margins black, a black dot on the outer side near the base; abdomen mottled with black spots and bars, the whole effect dark brown; all legs with very clearly defined black blotches and bands. the posterior surfaces of femora, white, metatarsi with 2 distinct black bands. Anterior tibiae with 7 pairs of inferior spines. Size TL6-9 mm (Lawrence 1940).

Anypops decoratus from Kloof Photo ASD

After Lawrence (1940)

Anyphops dubiosus (Lawrence, 1952)

COMMON NAME: Newcastle Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A KwaZulu-Natal endemic described Lawrence (1952) from Mullers Pass, Newcastle as *Selenops dubiosus*. The species is known only from two localities in KwaZulu-Natal (EOO<500 km²; AOO=8 km²; 1044-1189 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal:* Newcastle Muller's Pass (-27.75, 29.93); Ngome State Forest (-27.78, 31.45).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal spiders sampled from the Grassland (Haddad et al. 2013) and Forest biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are unknown. It receives some protection in the Ngome State Forest (Van der Merwe et al. 1996) but some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the female. Thoracic portion of carapace light brown with fine blackish lines, radiating from the fovea; cephalic portion darker, reddish-brown, the ocular area and clypeus blackish; mandibles dark reddish-brown, mouthparts brown, sternum ochre yellow; femora with small blackish spots above, patella with one basal, tibiae and metatarsi with two darker bands each, all these stronger on the dorsal than the ventral surface; abdomen above light brown variegated with numerous minute spots and stripes, below uniformly ochre yellow. Anterior tibiae with 6 inferior spines, II with 6-7 spines on one side; metatarsi with 3 inferior pairs of long spines, no lateral spines. Size TL 17 mm (Lawrence 1952).

After Lawrence (1952)

Abdomen after Corronca (unpublished)

Anyphops fitzsimonsi (Lawrence, 1940)

COMMON NAME: Mpumalanga Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Lawrence (1940) from Barberton in Mpumalanga as *Selenops fitzsimonsi*. The species has been sampled from three provinces (EOO=54 306 km²; AOO=44 km²; 270-1394 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Pretoria Wonderboom (-25.6939, 28.2025); Pretoria Welgegund (-23.83, 27.95); Pretoria Vredehuis (-25.737, 28.238). **Mpumalanga:** Barberton (-25.79, 31.04); Brondal (De Villiers) 20 km N E (-25.35, 30.84); Nelspruit, Hall & Sons, 10 km NE (-25.47, 30.96); Nelspruit Ou Stal, ARC-ITSC (-25.47, 30.96); Kalkfontein Farm Groblersdal (-25.25, 29.48); Lowveld National Botanical Garden (-25.47, 31.00); Sabie Bergvliet State Forest (-25.10, 31.78). **North West:** Rietfontein Brits (-25.62, 27.77).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal spiders sampled from the Savanna and Grassland biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013). The species has been sampled from trees in avocado, macadamia and citrus orchards and commercial pine plantations (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013). Specimens were also found in houses.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species and the species receives some protection in the Lowveld National Botanical Garden and Bergvliet State Forest.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the male. Carapace yellow-brown, without radiations from thoracic striae, a lighter parallel-sided broad yellow area behind the eyes as wide as the ocular row, bisected by the striae which is continued as a brown stripe on to the cephalic area; the broad median area of carapace bordered at the sides by a wavy brown line; eyes black; abdomen yellow above with a few indistinct brown markings; under surface and legs yellow, legs without black bands. Size TL 8.6 mm. Anterior tibiae with 6 pairs of inferior spines (Lawrence 1940).

Anyphops fitzsimonsi from Nelspruit Photo Aart Louw

Male palp after Lawrence (1940)

Anyphops gilli (Lawrence, 1940)

COMMON NAME: Uitenhage Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Lawrence (1940) from Uitenhage in the Eastern Cape as *Selenops gilli*. The species has been sampled from three provinces (EOO=88 547 km²; AOO=20 km²; 45-1307 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Hogsback, Amatola Mountains (-32.59, 26.92); Uitenhage (-33.725.37). *KwaZulu-Natal:* iSimangaliso Wetland Park (Hellsgate) (-28, 32.48); Ngome State Forest (-27.78, 31.45). *Western Cape:* Groeneweide Forest Station (-33.95 22.46); Diepwalle Forest Station (-34.03, 23.03).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal spiders sampled with pitfall traps and from leaf litter in dry-humid wet forest. Sampled from the Forest, Savanna (Foord et al. 2011) and Thicket biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. It is protected in three State Forests but more sampling needed to collect the female.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from only the male. Type specimens bleached. Carapace light reddish brown, a little darker anteriorly, thoracic stria brown, with some fine long radiating lines from it, cephalic area bisected by a light brown line which is duplicated for most of its length; mandibles a little darker than carapace; abdomen above with some brown spots and wavy cross-bars over most of its surface, near its posterior extremity a transverse, procurved, fairly broad black stripe. Anterior tibiae with 6 pairs of inferior spines. Size TL 8.6 mm (Lawrence 1940).

Male palp after Lawrence (1940)

Anyphops helenae (Lawrence, 1940)

COMMON NAME: St Helena Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described Lawrence (1940) as *Selenops helenae* and known only from the type locality Stompneus St. Helena Bay (EOO=4 km²; AOO=4 km²; 109 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape:* St. Helena Bay (-32.77, 18.03); Stompneus (-32.77, 18.03).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal spiders sampled from the Fynbos Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are unknown. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from only female. Carapace light reddish brown, ornamented with minute black specks and larger blackish spots, a tuft of white hairs above and overhanging the anterior median eyes; mandibles the same colour as the carapace; abdomen above brown with some rather ill-defined symmetrical darker markings; anterior legs with brown bands, posterior ones without. Anterior tibiae with 5 pairs of inferior spines. Size TL 8 mm (Lawrence 1940).

After Lawrence (1940)

Anypops hessei (Lawrence, 1940)

COMMON NAME: Hesse's Anypops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Lawrence (1940) as *Selenops hessei* from Matjiesfontein from the Western Cape. The species is sampled from three provinces including four protected areas (EOO=241 485 km²; AOO=32 km²; 250-1405 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex, it has a wide geographical range and is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Free State:** Smithfield (-30.21, 26.53). **Western Cape:** Anysberg Nature Reserve (-33.53, 20.76); Gamkaberg Nature Reserve (-33.31, 21.71); Matjiesfontein (-33.24, 20.58); Prince Albert (-33.22, 22.03); Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46). **Northern Cape:** Richtersveld National Park (-28.25 17.17); Noumees pools Helskloof (-28.30, 16.999); Hottentotsparadys (-28.3167, 17.00).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders. Sampled from the Fynbos, Desert, Grassland (Haddad et al. 2013) and Succulent Karoo biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. It is protected in the Anysberg Nature Reserve, Gamkaberg Nature Reserve, Karoo National Park and Richtersveld National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from only the female. Carapace reddish brown with a fine blackish marginal border, cephalic portion darker than the thoracic portion; thoracic striae and its radiations distinct, the remaining markings somewhat vague; chelicerae dark reddish brown, abdomen rubbed but apparently with a number of blackish-brown spots near the spinners; femora of legs with ill-defined banded markings, those of the tibiae more distinct, metatarsi dark brown. Anterior tibiae with 5 pairs of inferior spines. Size TL 13 mm (Lawrence 1940).

After Lawrence (1940)

Abdomen after Corronca (unpublished)

Anyphops hewitti (Lawrence, 1940)

COMMON NAME: Hewitt's Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern Africa endemic described by Lawrence (1940) as *Selenops hewitti* from Grahamstown. The species is presently known from two southern African countries. In South Africa known from two provinces (EEO=12 669 km²; AOO=16 km²; 556-1407 m a.s.l.). But due to its wide geographic range in southern Africa, the species is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Grahamstown (-33.3, 26.52); Grahamstown Flats (-33.17 26.31); 8 km N. of Grahamstown Beaufort road (-33.20, 26.35). *Limpo-po:* Wolkberg Wilderness Area Haenertsburg (-23.94, 29.95).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders sometimes found under stones. Sampled from the Savanna (Foord et al. 2011) and Thicket biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species but more sampling is needed to determine the species' range. It is protected in the Wolkberg Wilderness Area.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes. Carapace light brown with a narrow black margin; striae and some fine radiations from it black, some spots close to the lateral margins black, a pair of short anteriorly diverging black bars behind the posterior median eyes; mandibles light reddish brown; abdomen above with two transverse black recurved markings in its posterior half, area above the spinners blackish; legs with strong black bars, especially on the femur and base of tibia, these much fainter in the posterior legs. Anterior tibiae with 5 pairs of inferior spines. Size TL 8-9.5 mm (Lawrence 1940).

After Lawrence (1940)

Abdomen after Corronca (unpublished)

Anyphops immaculatus (Lawrence, 1940)

COMMON NAME: Gauteng's Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC.

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Lawrence (1940) as *Selenops immaculatus* from Florida in Gauteng. The species is known from five provinces including two protected areas (EOO=411 297 km²; AOO=40 km²; 52-1693 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Free State:** Bloemfontain Naval Hill (-28.09, 26.23); Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.62, 26.68). **Gauteng:** Florida (-26.18, 27.91); Pretoria (-25.74, 28.19); Pretoria Wonderboom South (-25.7017, 28.2031). **Eastern Cape:** Kei River Mouth (-32.68, 28.37); East London (-33.01, 27.90). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Cathedral Peak Rainbow Gorge (-28.94, 29.19). **Western Cape:** Swartberg Nature Reserve (-33.36, 21.69); Darling (-33.37, 18.39).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders sampled from the Fynbos, Grassland (Haddad et al. 2013) and Thicket biomes. Sometimes also found in houses.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. It is protected in the Swartberg Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2005) and Amanzi Private Game Reserve (Haddad & Butler 2018).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from only the male. Carapace yellow-brown, thoracic striae and some very faint radiations from it a little darker, eyes surrounded by a blackened area; mandibles yellow brown; abdomen yellow with a few blackish brown spots; legs without markings except for two very faint brown bands on the anterior tibiae. Anterior tibiae with 5 pairs of inferior spines. Size TL 8.5 mm (Lawrence 1940).

Anypops karrooicus (Lawrence, 1940)

COMMON NAME: Karoo's Anypops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: C

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Lawrence (1940) from Hanover as *Selenops karrooicus*. The species is known from a few localities in three provinces (EOO=40 203 km²; AOO=20 km²; 1259-1680 m a.s.l.). Still undersampled but with a wide geographical range the species is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Middelburg Grootfontein Research Station (-31.49, 24.99). **Free State:** Qwa Qwa National Park Avondrust (-28.29, 28.42); Luckhoff (-29.73, 24.77). **Northern Cape:** Hanover (-30.94, 24.53); Naauwpoort (-26.17, 25.57).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders found under stones sampled from the Grassland, Nama Karoo and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. It receives protection in the Qwa Qwa National Park (Golden Gate National Park) (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes. Carapace light reddish brown, sides narrowly bordered with black, ocular area blackish, thoracic portion with irregular stripes and spots, the radii from the thoracic striae blackish but in complete; cephalic portion bordered by narrow blackish lines and bisected by a narrow line; mandibles reddish brown; abdomen dull white or yellow dorsally, with symmetrical light-brown markings in the middle line, a darker transverse marking just above the spinners. Legs yellow, strongly banded with black except on their ventral surfaces; femora with 3 black bands, patellae with 1 basal band, tibiae with 2 bands. Size TL 9-17 mm (Lawrence 1940).

After Lawrence (1940)

Anypops karrooicus female Photo Allen Jones

Anyphops kraussi (Pocock, 1898)

COMMON NAME: Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: Rare

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described by Pocock (1898) as *Selenops kraussii* with type locality only Cape Colony. The species was sampled from various localities in indigenous forest areas on the Table Mountain National Park (EOO=62 km²; AOO=12 km²; 7-292 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex and to a small area it is therefore listed as Rare.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape:* Table Mountain National Park Fernwood Gully (-33.9798, 18.4311); Table Mountain National Park Newlands Forest (-33.91, 18.42); Table Mountain National Park Tokai (-34.05, 18.27); Bontebok National Park (-34.07, 20.45).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders sampled from indigenous forest in the Fynbos Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in the Table Mountain National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020) but more sampling needed.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the female. It resembles *Selenops radiatus* in size and colour. The legs are strongly banded. Species with 6 pairs of inferior tibial spines (Pocock 1898).

After Pocock (1898)

Abdomen and epigyne after Corronca (unpublished)

Anyphops kraussi from Bontebok National Park Photo-Elton le Roux

Anyphops kraussi Photo Heather Hodgson

Anyphops lawrencei (Roewer, 1951)

COMMON NAME: Zululand Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described by Lawrence (1947) as *Selenops pusillus*, but the name was preoccupied and Roewer (1951) provided a replacement name *Anyphops lawrencei*. In South Africa known from three provinces including six protected areas (EOO=109 418 km²; AOO=40 km²; 112-1920 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Zimbabwe, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Free State:** Golden Gate National Park, Avondrust-Suid (-28.23, 28.3). **Gauteng:** Irene Veld field opposite Gem Village (-25.868, 28.218); Klipriviersberg Nature Reserve (-26.308, 28.015); Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve (-26.48, 28.24); Rietvleidam Nature Reserve (-28.85, 28.16). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (-28.09, 32.1); Ngome State Forest (-27.78, 31.45); uMkhuze Game Reserve (-27.609, 32.227); Kloof (-29.78, 30.83).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders. Frequently sampled from under rocks in the Forest, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013). Van der Merwe (1994) surveyed five habitat types in the Ngome State Forest, South Africa, where he collected *A. lawrencei* from pitfall traps in open and dense indigenous forest.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. It is protected in the Klipriviersberg Nature Reserve, Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve, Golden Gate National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020), Rietvleidam Nature Reserve and uMkhuze Game Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised Corronca (2005). Known from both sexes. Carapace orange-brown with lateral dark grey markings; chelicerae orange-brown; legs pale orange-brown with markings on femora I–II forming two incomplete rings and femora III–IV with two pro-lateral dark grey parallel lines limiting a pale and narrow band; dorsum abdomen dark brown with yellowish spots and a typical posterior transversal light band; venter light grey. Anterior tibiae with 5 pairs of spines, anterior metatarsi with 3, femora above with 3 very long and more or less erect blackish spines. Size TL: 5-6 mm (Corronca 2005).

After Corronca (2005).

After Lawrence (1947)

Anyphops lawrencei from Irene Photo Peter Webb

Anyphops leleupi Benoit, 1972

COMMON NAME: Leleup's Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Benoit (1972) from Mariepskop in Mpumalanga. The species has also been sampled from several localities in two provinces (EOO=29 918 km²; AOO=36 km²; 762-1407 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known from one sex it has a wide geographical range and is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Limpopo:** Westphalia (-23.3, 29.18); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve Farm The Downs (-24.14, 30.31); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve Farm Malta (-24.17, 30.25); Wolkberg Wilderness Haenertsburg (-23.94, 29.95); Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.038, 29.442); Warmbaths/Bela-Bela (-24.88, 28.29); Hanglip Forest Reserve (-23.04, 29.91); Klein Kariba (-24.88, 28.29); Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04). **Mpumalanga:** Mariepskop (-24.58, 30.87); Magoebaskloof Hotel (-23.82, 30.06).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal spiders sampled from the Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011). The species was sampled from tree bark at Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. It is protected in the Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2016); Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2008), Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2019) and Hanglip Forest Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the female. Anterior tibiae with 6 pairs of inferior spines. Size TL 9.50 mm (Benoit 1972).

After Benoit (1972)

Epigyne photo ASD

Anyphops leleupi from Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve
Photo Peter Webb

Anyplops lesserti (Lawrence, 1940)

COMMON NAME: Touwsriver Anyplops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described by Lawrence (1940) as *Selenops lesserti* from Touws River. The species was sampled from a few localities in the province (EOO=2 595 km²; AOO=12 km²; 0-1405 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the female and to determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Western Cape: Gouritsmond, Borrelfontein, 8 km W (-34.34, 21.87); Touws River (-33.44, 21.18); Swartberg Nature Reserve Gamkaskloof Die Hel (-33.35, 21.67).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders sampled in the Fynbos Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are unknown. It receives some protection in the Swartberg Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2005). Some more sampling is needed to collect the female and to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from only the male. Carapace orange-yellow with the thoracic striae; mandibles much darker than carapace; reddish brown; abdomen light -yellow-brown above; with minute scattered black dots and a wavy transverse black stripe above the spinners; legs apparently without markings or bands of any kind. Anterior tibiae with 5 pairs of inferior spines. Size TL 10.2 mm (Lawrence 1940).

After Corronca (unpublished).

After Lawrence (1940)

Anyphops lignicola (Lawrence, 1937)

COMMON NAME: Hluhluwe Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic species described Lawrence (1937) as *Selenops lignicolus* from Hluhluwe Nature Reserve in KwaZulu-Natal. The species was sampled from a few localities in KwaZulu-Natal and Mpumalanga (EOO= 18 938 km²; AOO=16 km²; 83-1345 m a.s.l.). Due to this species having extensive habitat in protected areas and it is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal:* Hluhluwe (-28.02, 32.28); Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (-28.09, 32.1); Umfolosi Drift (-28.33, 31.08) uMkhuze Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25). *Mpumalanga:* Kruger National Park, Malelane Camp (-25.47, 31.52).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders. They are frequently sampled from pitfall traps in the Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. It is protected in the Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (Mgobozi et al. 2008), uMkhuze Game Reserve and Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Carapace brown, a V-shaped blackish marking behind the eyes, eyes infuscated, a dark spot behind the posterior lateral eyes; a dark median stripe on the cephalic portion; thoracic portion of carapace with a dark marginal and submarginal band, the latter incomplete. Abdomen above mottled, for the most part dark, with an indistinct median tree-like marking; Legs yellow with strongly contrasting irregular black bands (especially on the anterior pairs); patellae blackened in their basal halves; tibiae with 2 distinct black bands; metatarsi with 2 black, less distinct bands, the distal one at the apex of segment; femora below yellow; remaining legs faintly banded below; tibia and tarsus of palp with a distinct black basal band. Tibiae I and II with 5, metatarsi I and II with 3 pairs of strong inferior spines. Size TL 10.4 mm (Lawrence 1937).

Male from Malelane Photo ASD

Palp and carapace Photo ASD

Anyphops lochiel Corronca, 2000

COMMON NAME: Lochiel Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Corronca (2000) from Lochiel in Mpumalanga. The species is known from two provinces (EEO<500 km²; AOO=8 km²; 894-1599 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo*: Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04).

Mpumalanga: Lochiel (-26.15, 30.78)

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders sampled from the Savanna Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are unknown. It is protected in the Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2019) but some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from only the female. Carapace pale orange brown. Abdomen yellowish with grey spots. Anterior tibiae with 6 pairs of inferior spines. Size TL 10.3 mm. (Corronca 2000).

After Corronca (unpublished).

Anyphops longipedatus (Roewer, 1955)

COMMON NAME: Johannesburg Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Lawrence (1940) as *Selenops longipes* from Johannesburg in Gauteng. Name was preoccupied and a replacement name provided by Roewer (1955). The species was sampled from three provinces. (EOO=422 km²; AOO=12 km²; 1046-1762 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Johannesburg (-26.2, 28.04); Kempton Park (-26.09, 28.23). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ladysmith (-28.55, 29.76); Natal Midlands: Klipriver Dawns Pride (-28.55, 29.78). **North West:** Skeerpoort (25.81, 27.75).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders sampled from the Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are unknown. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from only the female. Specimens somewhat bleached. Carapace light yellow brown with indistinct spots and mottling, boundaries of cephalic area and striae a little darker, areas surrounding the eyes blackish, mandibles not darker than carapace; abdomen above with indistinct spots and mottling in the anterior half, two black bow-shaped transverse bars in posterior half; legs with indistinct blackish brown bands, those at the bases of the anterior tibiae and femora well defined. Anterior tibiae with 5 pairs of inferior spines. Size TL 9.5 mm (Lawrence 1940).

After Lawrence (1940)

Anyphops longipedatus from Kemptonpark Photo Warren Schmidt

Anyphops lucia Corronca, 2005

COMMON NAME: St Lucia Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A KwaZulu-Natal endemic described by Corronca (2005) from St. Lucia Fanie's Camp in the iSimangaliso Wetland Park (EOO=4 km²; AOO=4 km²; 5 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: KwaZulu-Natal: iSimangaliso Wetland Park: St. Lucia, Fanie's Camp (-28.36, 32.41); Umhlanga (-29.7, 31.09).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders sampled from the Indian Ocean Coastal Belt Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are unknown. The species receive some protection in the iSimangaliso Wetland Park but some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the female. Carapace red brown with lateral dark grey irregular markings reaching to the lateral edges; chelicerae red-brown with a wide longitudinal inner dark brown band; legs orange-brown, mottled dark grey; patellae II and IV with dark basal band and Fe IV with a prolateral and longitudinal pale line limited by grey parallel lines; metatarsus IV with a dark terminal spot; dorsum of abdomen whitish, dotted by grey irregular spots, lateral and posterior portion darker; venter pale yellow-grey. Anterior tibiae with 6 pairs of inferior spines. Size TL 7.73 mm (Corronca 2005).

After Corronca (2005).

Anyphops lucia from Umhlanga Photo Peter Webb

Anyphops lycosiformis (Lawrence, 1937)

COMMON NAME: Nkandla Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Lawrence (1937) as *Selenops lycosiformis* from Nkandla Forest in KwaZulu-Natal. The species is known from two provinces (EOO=13 774 km²; AOO=12 km²; 687-1129 m a.s.l.). Although only known from one sex this species has a wide enough distribution and occurs in a number of protected areas where it is not threatened therefore listed as Least Concerned.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ngome State Forest (-27.78, 31.45); Nkandla Forest (-28.61, 31.09). **Limpopo:** Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (-23.82, 30.16)

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders. Sampled from the Forest and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. Protected in two State Forests and the Legalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2016) but some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Corronca (2005). Only female known. Carapace orange-brown with a light middle central area; chelicerae orange-brown with dark marking in distal portion; legs pale orange-yellow with markings: three incomplete rings on femora and two on tibiae; metatarsi and tarsi pale yellowish; dorsum of abdomen pale brown with light yellowish central area; venter light yellow. Anterior tibiae with 4 pairs of inferior spines. Size TL 7.70 mm (Lawrence 1937).

Anyphops lycosiformis from Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve
Photo Peter Webb

After Lawrence (1937)

Anyphops maculosus (Lawrence, 1940)

COMMON NAME: Willowmore Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Lawrence (1940) as *Selenops maculosus* from Willowmore in the Eastern Cape. The species is known from three provinces (EOO=80 817 km²; AOO=20 km²; 709-1212 m a.s.l.) Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Willowmore (-33.3, 23.5); Pearston (-32.59, 25.15). **Northern Cape:** Farm Gamesep Postmasburg distr. (-27.45, 22.40); Kathu (-27.69, 23.06). **Western Cape:** Beaufort West (-32.35, 22.58); Karoo National Park Beaufort West (-32.28, 22.46).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders sampled from the Nama Karoo and Thicket biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species and is protected in the Karoo National Park but some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from only the female. Carapace with well-defined radiations from the thoracic striae and crenulated submarginal bands, a well-defined but narrow blackish marginal marking; mandibles reddish brown with some darker markings; abdomen above dirty yellow with some ill-defined brownish spots and a number of minute dots scattered over its surface; legs with fairly well defined bands. Anterior tibiae with 5 pairs of inferior spines. Size TL 11 mm (Lawrence 1940).

Anyphops maculosus from Kathu Photo Morne van Staden

After Lawrence (1940)

After Corronca (unpublished).

Anyphops marshalli (Pocock, 1902)

COMMON NAME: Estcourt Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A KwaZulu-Natal endemic described by Pocock (1902) from Estcourt as *Selenops marshalli*. The species is now known from three provinces (EOO= 129 612 km²; AOO=28 km²; 17-1189 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Grahamstown (-33.30, 26.52); East London Pineapple Research Station (-33.01, 27.90); Port Alfred (-33.58, 26.89). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Durban (-29.85, 31.01); Estcourt (-29, 29.87); Pinetown (-29.381, 30.85); Kloof (-29.78, 30.83). **Western Cape:** Diepwalle Forest Station (-33.95, 23.17).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders sampled from the Grassland (Haddad et al. 2013), Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011). It has also been sampled from houses.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. It is protected in the Diepwalle Forest Station. But some more sampling is needed to collect the female and to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Only the male known. Integument ochre-brown, covered with a mixture of golden-yellow and blackish hairs; legs with blackish bands. Anterior tibiae with 7 pairs of inferior spines. Size TL 11 mm (Pocock 1902).

Anyphops marshalli female from Kloof Photo Peter Webb

Pocock (1902)

After Corronca (unpublished).

Anyphops minor (Lawrence, 1940)

COMMON NAME: Empangeni Anyphops Wall Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Lawrence (1940) as *Selenops minor* from Empangeni in the KwaZulu-Natal. The species sampled from two provinces (EOO=53 388 km²; AOO=20 km²; 7-243 m a.s.l.). The species has a wide geographical range and is therefore listed as Least Concern

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **KwaZulu-Natal:** Empangeni (-28.72, 31.88); iSimangaliso Wetland Park: Hell's Gate (-28, 32.48); La Mercy (-29.63, 31.13). **Western Cape:** Diepwalle Forest Station (-34.03, 23.03); Groeneweide Forest Station, Groenkop, N E of George (-33.95, 22.46).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders sampled from the Forest, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011). It has also been sampled from sugar cane fields (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. It is protected in Diepwalle Forest Station and Groeneweide Forest Station.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes. Carapace brown with a very broad blackish-brown marginal band, crenulated along its inner margin and including some light brown spots; the lighter inner portion of the carapace without distinct radiations from the thoracic stria, a T-shaped blackish marking behind the eyes, the cephalic portion with a narrow blackish margin; mandibles blackish brown; abdomen blackish, variegated with a few symmetrically arranged lighter spots, a large pair just anterior to the posterior margin, some minute black spots at the sides of the under surface; femora of legs with only one complete well defined band in the middle, the other two bands represented by blotches and spots. Anterior tibiae with 5 pairs of inferior spines. Size TL 7.6 mm (Lawrence 1940).

After Corronca (unpublished).

After Lawrence (1940)

Anyphops montanus (Lawrence, 1940)

COMMON NAME: Clanwilliam Anyphops Wall Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described by Lawrence (1940) as *Selenops montanus* from Clanwilliam. The species is known from a few localities in the Western Cape all sampled prior to 1940 (EOO=3 151 km²; AOO=12 km²; 78-980 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' current range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Western Cape: Clanwilliam (-32.16, 18.89); Matroosberg (-33.42, 19.84); Great Winterhoek Mts. (-33.07, 19.09); Hermanus Moffat street (-34.4, 19.25).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders sampled from the Fynbos and Nama Karoo biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are unknown. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' current range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from only the female. Carapace light reddish brown with distinct radii from the thoracic stria, one of these passing straight forwards and terminating behind the median eyes; areas surrounding the eyes blackish; abdomen above with a number of minute brown dots forming chevrons, becoming more numerous posteriorly, otherwise uniformly light yellow; legs with black bands on tibiae. Tibia I and II with 6 pairs of extremely long and strong inferior spines; metatarsus I and II with 3 similar pairs of spines. Size TL 14.5 mm (Lawrence 1940).

After Lawrence (1940)

Photo Victor Hamilton-Attwell

Anyphops montanus from Hermanus Photo Victor Hamilton-Attwell

Anyphops mumai (Corronca, 1996)

COMMON NAME: Grahamstown Anyphops Wall Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An Eastern Cape endemic described by Lawrence (1940) as *Selenops minutus* but it was a primary junior homonym and Corronca (1996) provided a replacement name *Selenops mumai* from Grahamstown. The species is only known from localities in the Eastern Cape that was last sampled in 1991 from Fort Brown Kudu Reserve (EOO=8 km²; AOO=8 km²; 281-565 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the female and to determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Eastern Cape: Fort Brown Kudu Reserve Farm Hermanuskraal (-33.13, 26.62); Grahamstown (-33.3, 26.52).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders that were sampled in the Thicket Biome. In the Kudu Reserve sampled from pitfall traps.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are unknown. It is protected in the Fort Brown Kudu Reserve. Some more sampling is needed to collect the female and to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from only the male. Carapace reddish brown, with some submarginal markings, thoracic stria continued as a Y-shaped marking, cephalic area divided by a very faint narrow blackish stripe, eyes surrounded by blackened areas; chelicerae reddish brown; abdomen light brown, a broad, sharply defined, procurved band above the spinners, this transverse band whitish and contrasting strongly with the remainder of abdomen. Tibia I and II with 5, metatarsus I and II with 3 pairs of inferior spines; no lateral spines. Size TL 5.2 mm (Lawrence 1940).

After Lawrence (1940)

After Corronca (2005).

Anyphops namaquensis (Lawrence, 1940)

COMMON NAME: Namakwa Anyphops Wall Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Lawrence (1940) as *Selenops namaquensis* from Lekkersing in the Northern Cape. The species was sampled from two provinces (EOO=6 624 km²; AOO=16 km²; 234-751 m a.s.l.). Sampled from a poorly known part of the country where extensive natural habitat remains, it is suspected that this species occurs more widely in Namaqualand and therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa. (wrongly listed in WSC 2020 as Namibia).

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Northern Cape:** Lekkersing (-29, 17.09); Kamieskroon Namaqualand (-30.20, 17.93); Richtersveld National Park (-28.25, 17.17). **Western Cape:** 38 km N. of Bitterfontein (-31.03, 18.26).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders. Sampled from the Desert and Succulent Karoo biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. Protected in the Richtersveld National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes. Carapace light reddish brown, the thoracic striae with fine long black radiations from it, a short black bar behind each posterior lateral eye, an indistinct row of brown submarginal dots; mandibles a little darker than carapace; abdomen above light brown, darker posteriorly, with minute scattered black dots and a few large symmetrical spots above the spinners; legs differing from all the other species of this group in having one instead of two black bands on the tibiae, occupying the basal two-thirds of the segment, femora with vague brownish blotches; sides of patellae black, the remainder brown; anterior metatarsi black, the posterior ones lighter. Anterior tibiae with 5 pairs of inferior spines. Size TL: 9.2 mm (Lawrence 1940).

After Lawrence (1940)

Anyphops narcissi Benoit, 1972

COMMON NAME: Swaziland Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described by Benoit (1972) from Swaziland. In South Africa sampled from Mpumalanga in forest areas (EOO=8 818 km²; AOO=24 km²; 78-1382 m a.s.l.). Although only known from one sex the species is widespread enough across South Africa and Swaziland for it to be listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Swaziland and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Mpumalanga*: Mariepskop 15 km W. Klaserie (-24.55, 31.02); Drakensberg Mts 32 mi. W. Klaserie (-24. 61, 31.06); Sabie Bergvliet State Forest (-25.10, 30.78); Sappi Greystone Plantation Nylshoogte near Barberton (-25.95, 31.11). *KwaZulu-Natal*: University of Zululand Empangeni (-28.72, 31.88).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders. Sampled from pitfall traps from indigenous forest in state forest and plantations in the Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Grassland biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats are unknown. It is protected in the Sabie Bergvliet State Forest. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' current range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the female. The whole body and the legs pale yellow except the eyes dark circles. Abdomen yellow with a vague darker pattern on the distal half. Metatarsi I and II with three pairs of lower spines: a front row of five and a posterior row of six spines. Size TL 6.3 mm (Benoit 1972).

After Benoit (1972)

Anyplops natalensis (Lawrence, 1940)

COMMON NAME: Natal Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A KwaZulu-Natal endemic described by Lawrence (1940) as *Selenops natalensis* from Estcourt (EOO=4 km²; AOO=4 km²; 1189 m a.s.l.). The species is known only from the type locality. The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range. Therefore listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal*: Estcourt (-29, 29.87).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders sampled from the Grassland Biome (Haddad et al. 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are unknown but some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised Corronca (2005). Known from both sexes. Carapace blackish brown at the sides, with a median, more or less parallel, yellow marking (as wide as the darkened area on in front. each side); this lighter marking with crenulated sides and constricted behind the thoracic stria, reaching from the ocular area to the posterior margin and containing a blackish median stripe with a pair of lateral branches; abdomen above dark brown, a pair of long oval lighter markings on each side of the anterior half, a pair of smaller oval light spots above the spinners; legs with anterior tibiae with 4 pairs of inferior spines, anterior metatarsi with 3 inferior pairs, no lateral spines, anterior tibiae unusually short and stout. Size TL 8 mm (Lawrence 1940).

After Lawrence (1940)

After Corronca (2005b). After Corronca (2005a).

Anyphops ngome Corronca, 2005

COMMON NAME: Ngome Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Corronca (2005) from Ngome State Forest in KwaZulu-Natal. The species is known from two provinces (EOO=3 346 km²; AOO=12 km²; 839-1558 m a.s.l.). Currently only known from protected areas where it is not declining therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal:* Ithala Nature Reserve (-27.51, 31.23); Ngome State Forest (-27.78, 31.45). *Limpopo:* Vhembe Biosphere Hanglip State Forest (-22.998, 29.884).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders sampled from the ground in open and closed forests. Sampled from the Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. It is protected in two State Forests and the Ithala Nature Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes. Carapace light orange-brown with lateral dark grey markings, reaching lateral edges. Chelicerae orange-brown with a slight light grey marking. Legs orange-brown without markings. Dorsum of abdomen with a whitish, large, sub-rectangular marking on anterior and middle portion of the abdomen; laterals dark brown with yellowish spots. Venter light yellow-grey. Anterior tibiae with 4 pairs of inferior spines. Size TL 5.56 mm (Corronca 2005).

After Corronca (2005)

After Corronca (2005a). *Anyphops ngome* male from Ngome State Forest Photo ASD

Anyphops parvulus (Pocock, 1900)

COMMON NAME: Small Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Pocock (1900) as *Selenops parvulus* from Port Elizabeth. Known from single records from two provinces (EEO<500 km²; AOO=8 km²; 7-45 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa. (In WSC 2020 wrongly also listed from Congo)

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Port Elizabeth (-33.95, 25.61). *Western Cape:* Knysna, Kranshoek, 20 km E Knysna (-34.03, 23.03).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders sampled from the Forest and Thicket biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are unknown. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Corronca (2005). Known from only the female. Carapace orange-brown with lateral dark grey markings reaching the lateral edges, with a black external line. Chelicerae orange-brown with a slight dark grey marking on the inner edge and a transversal spot at its tip. Legs pale orange-brown with markings. Dorsum of abdomen pale grey with dark grey spots; laterals dark grey and posterior portion of the opisthosoma with a whitish transversal band. Anterior tibiae with 4 pairs of inferior spines. Size TL 7.07 mm (Corronca 2005).

After Corronca (2005a).

Anyphops phallus (Lawrence, 1952)

COMMON NAME: Pietermaritzburg Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A KwaZulu-Natal endemic described by Lawrence (1952) as *Selenops phallus* from Otto's Bluff Pietermaritzburg (EOO=4 km²; AOO=4 km²; 1668 m a.s.l.). The species is known only from the type locality. The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: KwaZulu-Natal: Pietermaritzburg, Otto's Bluff (-29.6, 30.38).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders sampled from the Savanna Biome Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION THREATS: Threats to the species are unknown. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes. Carapace reddish-brown, thoracic portion with two sub marginal crenulated darker bands, the inner wider than the outer one; cephalic portion with a V-shaped dark marking behind the eyes; mandibles reddish-brown with ill-defined darker markings; sternum, mouthparts and undersides of legs, ochre yellow; femora above with two crenulated darker bands, patellae with one, tibiae with two dark bands; abdomen above brown, with some symmetrical lighter patches, below ochre yellow. Anterior tibiae with 5 pairs of inferior spines, metatarsi with 3 inferior pairs, no lateral spines. Size TL 6 mm (Lawrence 1952).

After Lawrence (1952)

Anyhops pococki (Lawrence, 1940)

COMMON NAME: Lydenburg Anyhops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Lawrence (1940) as *Selenops pococki* from Lydenburg. The species is sampled from three provinces EOO=86 973 km²; AOO=20 km²; 91-1742 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex, it has a wide geographical range and is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal:* Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94; 32.47). *Mpumalanga:* Lydenburg (-25.09, 30.46); Warburton Jessievale Forest Station (-26.25, 30.53). *North West:* Rietfontein Brits (-26.62, 27.77).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal spiders sampled under bark of trees in the Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. It is protected in three protected areas: Ophathe Game Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2015), Tembe Elephant Park and Jessievale Forest Station. Some more sampling is needed to collect the female and to determine the species' current range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from only the male. Carapace dark brown with numerous darker spots and radiations, ocular area black; mandibles a little darker than carapace; abdomen yellow with blackish-brown symmetrical markings; legs with ill-defined markings, those of the femora strongest, those of the posterior legs almost obsolete. Tibia I and II with 5 pairs of inferior spines, 2 lateral spines on each side, and 3 superior spines; metatarsus I and II with 3 pairs of inferior spines and 2 lateral spines on each side. Size TL 9.4 mm. (Lawrence 1940).

Anyhops pococki male Photo ASD

After Lawrence (1940)

Male palp Photo ASD

Anyhops pococki undescrbed female Photo ASD

Anyphops purcelli (Lawrence, 1940)

COMMON NAME: Montagu Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Lawrence (1940) as *Selenops purcelli* from Montagu Bath in the Western Cape. The species is known from two provinces (EOO<2000 km²; AOO=8 km²; 1-222 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Mkambati Nature Reserve (31.32, 29.97).
Western Cape: Montagu Baths (-33.79, 20.13).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders. Sampled from the Fynbos Grassland (Haddad et al. 2013) and Indian Ocean Coastal Belt biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are unknown. It is protected in the Mkambati Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2011) but more sampling is needed to collect the male.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from only the female. Type specimen faded. Carapace yellow brown with a blackish marginal border; thoracic striae brown, a number of short blackish stripes near the lateral margins directed towards, but not connected with the striae; cephalic portion defined posteriorly by a blackish V-shaped marking; abdomen blackish brown above, rather rubbed, but with a clearly defined broad V-shaped marking above the spinners; legs with large black blotches on the antero-inferior surfaces of the anterior femora, and wide brown bands on the tibia, these markings becoming fainter in the posterior legs. Tibia I and II with 5, metatarsus I and II with 3 pairs of inferior spines. Size TL 8 mm (Lawrence 1940).

After Lawrence (1940)

Anyphops regalis (Lawrence, 1940)

COMMON NAME: Knysna Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described by Lawrence (1940) as *Selenops regalis* from Knysna. Another specimen from the Western Cape was collected from the Groeneweide Forest Station near George (EOO<500 km²; AOO=8 km²; 45-243 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape:* Knysna (-34.03, 23.03); Groeneweide Forest Station Groenkop N.E. of George (-33.95, 22.46).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders sampled from the Forest Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are unknown. It is partly protected in Groeneweide Forest Station. But some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from only the female. Carapace brown, a roughly circular patch in the middle of the posterior half much lighter, a few fine radiations from the thoracic stria; eyes surrounded by blackened area; mouthparts dark; abdomen above mottled brown; all legs with well-defined dark bands on both femora and tibiae. Anterior tibiae with 6, anterior metatarsi with 3 pairs of inferior spines. Size TL 12 mm (Lawrence 1940).

After Lawrence (1940)

Anyphops regalis from Knysna Photo ASD

Anypops reservatus (Lawrence, 1937)

COMMON NAME: Hluhluwe Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Lawrence (1937) as *Selenops reservatus* from Hluhluwe Game Reserve. The species has been recorded from two provinces (EOO=106 131 km²; AOO=24 km²; 51-1148 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal:* Hluhluwe (-28.02, 32.28); Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (-28.09, 32.1); iSimangolisa Wetland Park Kosi Bay (-26.93, 32.87); iSimangolisa Wetland Park uMkhuze Game Reserve (-27.6093, 32.2273). *Limpopo:* Warmbaths Klein Kariba (-24.88, 28.29); Soutpansberg Hanglip Forest (-23.04, 29.91)

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders sampled from the Forest, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. It is protected in the uMkhuze Game Reserve and Hluhluwe Nature Reserve. But some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from only the female. Carapace pale, covered with white and yellow hairs and without dark markings; abdomen dorsally pale, almost yellow, covered with yellow, white and reddish hairs, with a few darker ones; no distinct pattern marking; sides of abdomen becoming progressively darker posteriorly; legs with femora yellow with a few darker spots, all remaining segments light yellow, punctuated with small dark brown spots. Tibia and tarsus of palp with an indistinct dark basal band. Size TL 11.5 mm (Lawrence 1937).

After Lawrence (1937)

Anyphops rubicundus (Lawrence, 1940)

COMMON NAME: Belfast Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Lawrence (1940) as *Selenops rubicundus* from Witpoort near Belfast in Mpumalanga. The species was sampled from three provinces (EOO=38 069 km²; AOO=24 km²; 285-1871 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South African.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Limpopo:** Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02). **Mpumalanga:** Belfast, Witpoort (-25.69, 30.04); Brondal, (De Villiers) 20 km NE (-25.35, 30.84); Nelspruit, Hall & Sons, 10 km N E (-25.47, 30.96); Nelspruit ARC-ITSC (-25.47, 30.96). **Western Cape:** Swartberg Nature Reserve, Die Hel, Gamkaskloof (-33.36, 21.69).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders sampled from the Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011). The species also occurs abundantly in the avocado and macadamia orchards.(Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. It is protected in two protected areas: Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy 2003) and Swartberg Nature Reserve (Dippenaar- Schoeman et al. 2005). But some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from only the female. Carapace yellow-brown, cephalic area not darker than thoracic area; a marginal and submarginal row of ill-defined blackish Spots; thoracic striae continued on to the cephalic area as a fine blackish median line with a lateral branch on each side; eye area blackened ; mandibles with their inner halves blackened, the remainder coloured as in the carapace; abdomen with a symmetrical pattern of black spots intermixed with red hairs; femora of legs with black irregular spots tending to merge into each other as stripes; tibiae and metatarsi with weakly defined dark bands. Tibia I and II with 7, metatarsus I and II with 3 inferior pairs of spines. Size TL 13 mm (Lawrence 1940).

After Lawrence (1940)

Anyphops rubicundus from Swartberg Nature Reserve Photo J Hilton

Anyphops schoenlandi (Pocock, 1902)

COMMON NAME: Jansenville Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An Eastern Cape endemic described by Pocock (1902) as *Selenops schönlandi* from Jansenville in the Eastern Cape. The species has been sampled from several localities in the province (EOO=5 313 km²; AOO=16 km²; 39-778 m a.s.l.). Much natural habitat remains within its range and it is likely to be undersampled, therefore even though it is only known from one sex it is listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Eastern Cape: Addo Elephant National Park (-33.55, 25.69) Graaff-Reinet (-32.24, 24.53); Jansenville (-32.93, 24.67); Pearston (-32.59, 25.15).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders. Sampled from the Nama Karoo and Thicket biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are unknown. It is protected in the Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar -Schoeman et al. 2020). But some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from only the female. Carapace reddish brown with a narrow black margin; cephalic portion bisected by a fine black line, a branch from the middle of this line running to the base of each posterior median eye; abdomen above thickly covered with blackish-brown symmetrical blotches and markings; the sides more dotted, a broad transverse bow-shaped light marking above the spinners, separated from them by a black wavy transverse bar; legs with strong black bands. Anterior tibiae with 5, anterior metatarsi with 3 pairs of inferior spines. Size: TL 12.8 mm (Lawrence, 1940).

Anyphops septemspinatus (Lawrence, 1937)

COMMON NAME: Kosi Bay Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described by Lawrence (1937) as *Selenops septemspinatus* from Kosi Bay Nature Reserve. The species is also known from Mozambique. In South Africa sampled from two provinces (EOO=81 152 km²; AOO=28 km²; 4-1152 m a.s.l.) Due to the wide geographical range, the species is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Mozambique and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal:* iSimangaliso Wetland Park: Hell's Gate (-28, 32.48); iSimangaliso Wetland Park: Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87); iSimangaliso Wetland Park Fanie's Island (-28.10, 32.45); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.544, 32.155); Van Reenen (-28.37, 29.38); Estcourt (-29.00, 29.87). *Limpopo:* Sekhukhunelan Dist. Serunecjar-cave (-24.65, 30.32).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal spiders sampled from the Grassland, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Savanna Biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013). At iSimangaliso Wetland Park they were sampled from blue tsetse fly traps and under bark. In Limpopo sampled from a cave from the twilight zone near the entrance. At Ndumo Game Reserve found associated with fever tree bark (Haddad 2016).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. It is protected in the Tembe Elephant Park (Haddad et al. 2010), Kosi Bay Nature Reserve and Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad et al. 2006).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes. Carapace at the sides with irregular but distinct black markings; in the middle just anterior to the cephalic striae two black dots; a distinct black spot behind each posterior lateral eye; another at the sides of these eyes bordering the edge of the carapace; chelicera yellow, their inner margins and distal third black, a black spot on the outer side at their bases; abdomen above mottled with symmetrical dark markings, in the middle roughly chevron-shaped markings, a white A-shaped marking on each side near the spinners; legs with very black, strongly contrasting markings, anterior surfaces of femora I and II with 2 irregular very black bands, posterior surfaces without markings. Tibial I and II with 7 pairs of inferior spines, metatarsi I and II with 3 pairs. Size TL 10.4 mm (Lawrence 1937).

A. septemspinatus female and male from Ndumo Photo Charles Haddad

After Lawrence (1937)

After Lawrence (1937)

A. septemspinatus imm male from Ndumo Photo Rudi Steenkamp

Anyphops sexspinatus (Lawrence, 1940)

COMMON NAME: Concordia Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Northern Cape endemic described by Lawrence (1940) as *Selenops sexspinatus* from Concordia in the Northern Cape. The species has been sampled from several localities in the Northern Cape but most records were taken prior to 1940 except ones from the Richtersveld National Park and Namaqua National Park (EOO=9 003 km²; AOO= 20 km²; 182-1342m a.s.l.). Much natural habitat remains within its range and it is likely to be undersampled, therefore even though it is only known from one sex it is listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa. (Wrongly listed in WSC as from Namibia)

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Northern Cape: Concordia (-29.53, 17.94); Kamieskroon (-30.20, 17.93); Leliefontein (-30.3, 18.07); Richtersveld Transfrontier National Park (-28.25, 17.17); Namaqua National Park (-30.05, 17.35).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders sampled from the Desert and Succulent Karoo biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. It is protected in the Richtersveld National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020) and Namaqua National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020). But some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from only the female. Specimen bleached. Carapace light yellow-brown, darker anteriorly than posteriorly; thoracic stria, the boundaries of the cephalic area, and the areas surrounding the eyes brown, darker than the remainder; radiations from the stria faint; abdomen above bleached or rubbed; all legs with distinct bands, especially on the tibiae. Tibia I and II with 6, metatarsus I and II with 3 pairs of inferior spines. Size TL: 14.5 mm (Lawrence 1940).

After Lawrence (1940)

Immature female from Namaqua National Park
Photo ASD

Anyphops silvicollellus (Strand, 1913)

COMMON NAME: Krugerpark Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Strand (1913) as *Selenops silvicollella* from Rwanda. The species is sampled from four African countries. In South Africa sampled from Limpopo (EOO<1000 km²; AOO=8 km²; 418-1245 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range in Africa, the species is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Democratic Republic of the Congo, Rwanda, Tanzania and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo*: Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (-24.17, 30.25).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders sampled from trees in the Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. It is protected in two protected areas: Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2016) and Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy 2003).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes. Tibias I and II with seven pairs of inferior spines, large, rectangular genital plate with two incisions at the upper edge. Size: TL 8-12 mm (Benoit 1968).

After Benoit (1968)

Anyphops silvicollellus male from Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve Photo ASD

Anyphops spenceri (Pocock, 1896)

COMMON NAME: Spencer's Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Pocock (1896) as *Selenops spenceri* from Durban in KwaZulu-Natal. The species is known from three provinces (EOO=356 699 km²; AOO=52 km²; 17-1412 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Addo Elephant National Park (-33.55, 25.69); Baviaanskloof Nature Reserve (-33.76, 24.81); Blue cliff (Uitenhage) (-33.49, 25.46); Grahamstown (-33.3, 26.52); Keurkloof, Farm Ferndale (Baviaanskloof) (-33.68, 24.83); Manubi (-32.43, 28.57); Port St. Johns (-31.63, 29.53); Umtata (-31.58, 28.77). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Durban (-29.85, 31.01; Estcourt (-29, 29.87); Mfongosi (-27.28, 32.15); Winkelspruit (30.08, 30.83). **Limpopo:** Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders sampled from the Grassland, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Savanna and Thicket biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. It is protected in the Baviaanskloof Nature Reserve, Addo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al 2020) and Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2002). But some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from only the female. Colour yellowish brown; carapace partially clothed with white hairs, which, contrasting with the yellow of the integument gives it a mottled appearance; a fine dark line on lateral edges; region of the eyes deeply pigmented with black; abdomen thickly mottled above with fine brown and white spots; clothed with whitish hairs below. Legs with faintly variegated with stripes; tibiae of first and second legs with 7 pairs of inferior spines, protarsi with 3 pairs. Size TL 11 mm (Pocock 1896).

After Lawrence (1940)

Anyphops spenceri female from Baviaanskloof Nature Reserve Photo ASD

Anyphops stauntoni (Pocock, 1902)

COMMON NAME: Stauntoni's Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Pocock (1902) as *Selenops stauntoni* from Durban in KwaZulu-Natal. It has also been sampled from St Helena. In South Africa it is known from four provinces including five protected areas (EOO= 350 345 km²; AOO=176 km²; 4-1588 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range, the species is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: St. Helena and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Bashee Bridge (-31.91, 28.43); East London (-33.01, 27.9); Grahamstown (-33.3, 26.52); Kentani (-32.5, 28.32); Mzimhlava river mouth (-31.37, 29.58); Noziyongwana (-31.2167, 28.6833); East London (-33.01, 27.90); Jeffreysbay (-34.06, 24.91). **Gauteng:** Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Pretoria La Montagne (-25.7017, 28.2031). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Bluff (-29.88, 31.02); Durban (-29.85, 31.01); Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87); Nkandla Forest (-28.61, 31.09); Ngome State Forest (-27.78, 31.45); Pietermaritzburg (-29.6, 30.38); Port Shepstone (-30.74, 30.44); Richards Bay (15 km N) (-28.78, 32.1); Umhlali (-29.47, 31.22); Klip River Dawns Pride Farm (-28.55, 29.78); Pinetown (-29.81, 30.85); Empangeni (-28.72, 31.88); Greytown (-29.05, 30.60); Vernon Crookes Nat. Res. (-30.27, 30.57); Ekombe Forest 39 mi. N of Kranskop (-28.62, 30.87); Port St Johns (-31.63, 29.53); Drakensberg Little Switzerland Hotel (-28.72, 29.52); Emakabeleni 8 mi. N. Kranskop (-28.850, 30.8167); Sheffield Beach (-29.46, 31.26); Dargle (-29.54, 29.97); Illovo (-30.12, 30.85); Umfolosi (-28.50, 31.1667); Karkloof (-29.301, 30.21); Ifafa (-30.45, 30.64); Ingwavuma (-27.12, 32.01); New Hanover (-29.35, 30.52); Nottingham (-29.35, 30.00); Richmond (-29.86, 30.26); Port Edward (-31.04, 30.21); Uvongo S. Coast (-30.82, 30.39); uMkhuze Game Reserve (-27.609, 32.227). **North West:** Brits, Farm Rietfontein (-25.62, 27.77).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living nocturnal ground living spiders. The species was sampled from a variety of habitats in the Forest, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Grassland, Savanna and Thicket biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013). Van der Merwe (1994) surveyed five habitat types in the Ngome State Forest, South Africa, where *A. stauntoni* were sampled from pitfall traps in open and dense indigenous forest respectively.

After Lawrence (1937)

Anyphops stauntoni from Pretoria Photo Peter Webb

***Anyphops stauntoni* (continued)**

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. It is protected in Kosi Bay Nature Reserve, Vernon Crookes Nature Reserve, uMkhuze Game Reserve and several State Forest areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes. Colour of carapace with a broad, almost parallel-sided light band in the middle, constricted near the posterior border; sides with a blackish band a little narrower than the median band; mandibles blackish, sternum and coxae light, mouthparts light brown; abdomen above without pattern, the posterior half darker than the anterior, a broken black band at its anterior apex; sides blackish, especially posteriorly; undersurface light. Legs variegated with distinct black bands, anterior pairs with a distinct black band distal to the middle of the femora, tibiae with a basal and a middle black band, metatarsi with a basal and an apical black band; tibia and tarsus of pedipalp with a distinct basal black band. Tibiae I and II with 6 pairs of inferior spines, metatarsi with 3 pairs. Size TL 8.5 mm (Pocock (1902)).

Anyphops stauntoni from Karkloof Photo Rudi Steenkamp

***Anyphops stridulans* (Lawrence, 1940)**

COMMON NAME: Steinkopf Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Northern Cape endemic described by Lawrence (1940) as *Selenops stridulans* from Steinkopf (EOO=4 km²; AOO=4 km²; 870 m a.s.l.). The species is known only from the type locality. The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the female and to determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Northern Cape*: Steinkopf (-29.25, 17.73).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders. Sampled from under stones in the Succulent Karoo Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are unknown. Some more sampling is needed to collect the female and to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, known from only the male. Carapace pale yellow, almost without markings, a few indistinct darker spots near the lateral margin, a dark bar behind each eye surrounded by large black areas; abdomen yellow, a few minute spots at the sides of the posterior extremity; legs yellow with a few indistinct blackish spots and stripes. Tibia I and II with 6 pairs of inferior spines, some of them extremely long, 2 lateral spines on each side and 4-5 superior spines; metatarsus I and II with 3 pairs of inferior spines and 2 lateral spines on each side in basal half. Size TL 7-8 mm Lawrence (1940).

After Lawrence (1940)

After Corronca (unpublished)

Anyphops thornei (Lawrence, 1940)

COMMON NAME: Cedarberg Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described by Lawrence (1940) as *Selenops thornei* from the Cedarberg. The species has been sampled from several localities in the Cedarberg Wilderness Area (EOO=27 km²; AOO=8 km²; 78-1576 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Western Cape: Cedarberg Wilderness Area Mts. (-32.16, 18.89); Cedarberg Wilderness Area Sneeuokop 10.1 1605 m a.s.l. (-32.3554, 19.1525); Cedarberg Wilderness Area Sneeuokop 13.4 1570 m a.s.l.(-32.3490, 19.1708); Vredenburg Olifantskraal (-32.90, 17.99)

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders sampled from the Fynbos Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species not known. It is protected in the Cedarberg Wilderness Area (Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2016). Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Last revised by Benoit (1968). Known from only the female. Carapace light yellow-brown, a broad margin on each side a little darker; thoracic striae and boundaries of cephalic area clearly defined; abdomen infuscate above, becoming darker posteriorly, a narrow median light stripe in anterior two thirds and two small, well-defined, circular, whitish patches above the spinners, each containing a minute brown dot. Tibia I and II with 5 pairs of weak inferior spines, metatarsus I and II with 3 pairs of inferior spines. Size TL 7.3 (Lawrence 1940) .

After Lawrence (1940)

Anyphops thornei female from Cedarberg Photo Ant West

Anyphops transvaalicus (Lawrence, 1940)

COMMON NAME: Transvaal Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An Mpumalanga endemic described by as *Selenops transvaalicus* from Lydenburg. Sampled from a few localities in the province (EOO=9 793 km²; AOO=12km²; 163-1415 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Much natural habitat remains within its range and it is likely to be undersampled, therefore even though it is only known from one sex it is listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Mpumalanga*: Komatipoort (-25.43, 31.94); Lydenburg (-25.09, 30.46); Lydenburg Sterkspruit (-25.52, 27.37)/.

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders samped from the Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. But more sampling is needed to collect the male.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Last revised by Benoit (1968). Known from only the female. Carapace reddish brown; cephalic portion hardly darker than the rest, with a trident-shaped marking in the middle behind the median eyes; thoracic portion with the radiations of the striae ill-defined, each bearing a blackish dot in the middle, a few- brown dots near the marginal border which is not well defined; abdomen with some large ill-defined blackish-brown markings above; legs with weak and ill-defined dark bands. Anterior tibiae with 6 pairs of inferior spines. Size TL 11.4 mm (Lawrence 1940).

After Lawrence (1940)

After Corronca (unpublished)

Anyphops tuckeri (Lawrence, 1940)

COMMON NAME: Tucker's Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Lawrence (1940) as *Selenops tuckeri* from the Junction at Crocodile and Marico Rivers in North West. The species was also sampled from six provinces including four protected areas (EEO=292 956 km²; AOO= 64 km²; 219-1579 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex, it has a wide geographical range and is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Lusikisiki District Mzimhlava river mouth (-31.37, 29.58). **Free State:** Soutpan (-28.71, 26.06). **Gauteng:** Pretoria/Tshwane: Meyerspark, Pretoria (-25.74, 28.314), Wonderboom South (-25.70, 28.20), Rietondale Research Station (-25.73, 28.23); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36); Welgegund (-23.83, 27.95); Tswaing Crater Nature Reserve (-25.42, 28.08). **Limpopo:** Naboomspruit (-24.52, 28.71); Mosdene Nature Reserve (-24.3850, 28.3949). **Mpumalanga:** Barberton, Dracula's Castle (-25.79, 31.04); Bergvliet Forest Station (-25.1, 30.78); Nelspruit (-25.34, 31.77). **North West:** Junction Crocodile & Marico Rivers (-24.19, 26.87); Rustenburg, Donkerhoek (-25.65, 27.22); Rustenburg Nature Reserve (-25.72, 27.18).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal spiders sampled from the Forest, Grassland, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013), also found in buildings.

CONSERVATION THREATS: There are no known threats to the species. It is protected in Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve, Tswaing Crater Nature Reserve, Mosdene Nature Reserve and Rustenburg Nature Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Last revised by Benoit (1968). Known from only the female. Carapace light reddish brown with indistinct markings, thoracic striae and sides of the cephalic area darker, a faint stripe in the middle of the cephalic area bifurcating half-way between the eyes and the stria, eyes surrounded by black areas; abdomen light yellow with symmetrical brown markings. Tibia I and II with 6, metatarsus I and II with 3 pairs of long inferior spines. Size TL 10.3 mm (Lawrence (1940).

Anyphops tuckeri from Free state Photo Allen Jones

After Lawrence (1940)

After Corronca (unpublished)

***Anyphops tugelanus* (Lawrence, 1942)**

COMMON NAME: Tugela Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A KwaZulu-Natal endemic described by Lawrence (1942) as *Selenops tugelanus* from Middeldrift Tugela River (EOO=4 km²; AOO=4 km²; 212 m a.s.l.) The species is known only from the type locality. The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal*: Middeldrift, Tugela River (-28.898, 31.026).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders sampled from the Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION THREATS: Threats to the species are unknown. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Last revised by Benoit (1968). Known from only the female. Carapace with irregular indistinct spots and radiating stripes, those at the lateral margins more distinct, 3 short brown longitudinal bars behind the posterior median eyes; chelicerae yellow, a darker spot at their anterior apices and one basally at their sides; femora of legs with indistinct annulations, tibiae and metatarsi with 2 distinct but not very dark bands, ventral surfaces of legs uniformly yellow. Tibiae I and II with 7 pairs of inferior spines, the apical pair smaller than the others; metatarsi I and II with 3 pairs of inferior spines. Size TL: 13 mm (Lawrence 1942).

After Lawrence (1942)

After Corronca (unpublished)

Anyphops whiteae (Pocock, 1902)

COMMON NAME: White's Anyphops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Pocock (1902) as *Selenops whiteae* from Brak Kloof, Grahamstown. The species is known from two provinces (EOO=19 190 km²; AOO=28 km²; 5-607 m a.s.l.). Much natural habitat remains within its range and it is likely to be undersampled, therefore even though it is only known from one sex it is listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Grahamstown, Brak Kloof (-33.3, 26.52); King William's Town, Pirie Forest (-32.88, 27.39); Port St. Johns (-31.63, 29.53); Lusikisiki District Mzimhlava river mouth (-31.37, 29.58). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Pinetown near Durban (-29.81, 30.85); Umkomaas (-30.20, 30.80); Winklespruit (-30.10, 30.85).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders sampled from the Forest, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Savanna (Foord et al. 2011) and Thicket biomes.

CONSERVATION THREATS: There are no known threats to the species.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Last revised by Benoit (1968). Known from only the female. Colour: Carapace light yellow in the thoracic region, with a number of ill-defined darker lines radiating from the striae; cephalic portion darker, light reddish brown, bisected by a discontinuous median blackish stripe; ocular area in general blackish brown; mandibles yellow; blackish towards their apices; abdomen brown with some darker broad chevron markings, femora with blotched markings, tibia with ill-defined brown bands, metatarsi with strong blackish bands (a black band at apex and base, a yellow between them). Size TL 13.7 mm (Pocock 1902).

GENUS *SELENOPS* Latreille, 1819

The genus *Selenops* Latreille, 1819 is known from 132 species (World Spider Catalog 2020). Many of the original described *Selenops* species was moved to *Anyphops* a genus erected by Benoit (1968). From South Africa 13 *Selenops* species are known.

COMMON NAME: Selenops Flatties or Wall Spiders.

TYPE SPECIES: *Selenops radiatus* Latreille, 1819

MORPHOLOGY: *Selenops* differ from other selenopid genera by the arrangement of the eyes; the anterior median eyes, posterior median eyes and anterior lateral eyes align or are slightly recurved. Leg II > leg IV and tibiae I and II with 2-2-2 ventral spines and metatarsi I-II with 2-2 spines. They are usually brown to reddish brown spiders with dark spots. Small to large (6-23 mm) spiders. Carapace flattened; subcircular; usually brown to reddish brown, with lateral dark bands or spots; chelicerae brown to orange, normally with black or grey bands; labium and sternum usually paler in colour. Abdomen flattened, round to oval; clothed in dense setae; normally grey or yellowish with brown or black dorsal defined patterns; venter yellowish, without markings. Leg two claws with claw tufts and scopulae; laterigrade; anterior legs provided with strong, four to seven pairs of ventral spines on tibiae and metatarsi I and II; tarsal claws smooth; formulae normally 4321.

LIFESTYLE: They are free-living, agile spiders found on rocks, walls and tree trunks. With their very flattened bodies they are able to move into narrow crevices. Different species frequently occur sympatrically but occupy different microhabitats. The egg sac is round, flat, and papery that are attached to stones or bark (Croeser 1979).

TAXONOMY: The genus was studied by Lawrence (1940), Benoit (1968) and Corronca (2002, 2005).

Selenops sp. Photo Peter Webb

Selenops ansieae Corronca, 2002

COMMON NAME: Waterberg Selenops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Limpopo endemic described by Corronca (2002) from the Waterberg, Vygeboompoort. Also sampled from one other locality in the province (EOO<500 km²; AOO=8 km²; 840-1467m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo*: Waterberg, Vygeboompoort (-24.33, 28.33); Lephahlale/Ellisras (-23.67, 27.71).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders from the Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION THREATS: Threats to the species are unknown. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the female. Carapace orange-brown. Chelicerae orange. Legs orange-brown with dark incomplete rings on femora I-IV and tibiae I-IV; venter yellowish. SizeTL 8.78 mm (Corronca 2002).

After Corronca (2002)

Selenops ansieae female from Lephahlale Photo Peter Webb

Selenops brachycephalus Lawrence, 1940

COMMON NAME: Zimbabwe Selenops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described by Lawrence (1940) in Zimbabwe. In South Africa sampled from two provinces (EOO=28 583 km²; AOO=28 km²; 211-1372 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Zimbabwe and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo*: Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Luvuvhu Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Little Leigh (Western Soutpansberg) (-22.95, 29.87); Kruger National Park (Bateleur) (-23.234, 31.202); Goro Game Ranch near Vivo (-22.99, 29.43); Kruger National Park (Letaba) (-23.83, 31.58). *Mpumalanga*: Kruger National Park (Camp Shonga/Shamu) (-25.35, 31.99).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders sampled from the Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. Protected in the Blouberg Nature Reserve, Luvuvhu Nature Reserve and Kruger National Park. But some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Corronca (2002). Known only from the female. Carapace brown with some darker markings radiating forwards and sideways from thoracic stria, those in cephalic portion more strongly defined; abdomen above dark mottled brown, a few white speckles among the predominating brown ones; legs brown with some vague bands. Size TL 10-12 mm (Lawrence 1940).

Selenops brachycephalus female from Blouberg Nature Reserve

After Lawrence (1940)

Selenops dilon Corronca, 2002

COMMON NAME: Nelspruit Selenops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Corronca (2002) from Nelspruit in Mpumalanga. The species was sampled from two provinces (EOO=9 353km²; AOO=12 km²; 292-677 m a.s.l.). Much natural habitat remains within its range and it is likely to be under sampled, therefore even though it is only known from one sex it is listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo*: Pafuri (Waller's Camp) (-22.42, 30.91). *Mpumalanga*: Nelspruit (-25.47, 30.96); Kruger National Park (Silvervis Dam) (-24.01, 31.48).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal, ground living spiders sampled from the Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011). The species has also been sampled in citrus orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are unknown. It is protected in the Kruger National Park

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from only the female. Carapace reddish-brown; chelicerae dark brown-red; legs brown with tibiae, metatarsi and tarsi darker; femora I-IV with pale brown prolateral band and a circular prolateral distal area with white hairs. Abdomen brown-yellow with dark spots, venter pale brown. Size TL 14.00 mm (Corronca 2002).

Selenops dilon female from Kruger National park Photo ASD

After Corronca (2002)

Selenops feron Corronca, 2002

COMMON NAME: Baviaanspoort Selenops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described Corronca (2002) from Baviaanspoort in Gauteng. The species is known from three southern African countries. In South Africa known only from the type locality in Gauteng (EOO=4 km²; AOO=4 km²; 1297 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia, Zimbabwe and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Gauteng*: Baviaanspoort (-25.67, 28.37).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders. Sampled from under rocks in the Grassland Biome (Haddad et al. 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from female. Carapace brown with broad pale central marking; faint striae radiating forwards and sideways from fovea; abdomen above with dark median area; dark mottled brown on sides, a few white speckles among the predominating brown ones; legs brown with some vague bands. Size TL 9-10 mm (Corronca 2002).

After Corronca (2002)

Selenops feron Photo Koos Geldenhuys

Selenops ilcuria Corronca, 2002

COMMON NAME: Ellisras Selenops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Corronca (2002) from Marken in the Limpopo Province. The species has also been sampled from the Cameroon and is probably under sampled and expected to occur in more countries in between. In South Africa known from two provinces (EEO=7 084 km²; AOO=12 km²; 1001-1346 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range in Africa and is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Cameroon and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo*: Marken near Ellisras (-23.59, 28.39); Warmbaths/Bela-Bela, Klein Kariba (-24.88, 28.29). *Mpumalanga*: Loskop Dam Nature Reserve (-25.46, 29.23); Wakkerstroom (-27.33, 30.14).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders sampled from the Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. It is protected in the Loskop Dam Nature Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from female. Carapace and chelicerae dark reddish-brown. Legs brown, femora with three, and tibiae with two dark grey incomplete rings. Abdomen with tufts of white hairs, colour pattern pale yellowish- brown with small black spots, venter yellowish. Size TL 11.20 mm (Corronca 2002).

After Corronca (2002)

Selenops ilcuria from Wakkerstroom Photo Peter Webb

Selenops intricatus Simon, 1910

COMMON NAME: Selenops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Simon (1910) from Guinea-Bissau. Recorded from five African countries. In South Africa known from KwaZulu-Natal (EOO=4 km²; AOO=4 km²; 221 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range in Africa, the species is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Democratic Republic of the Congo, Guinea-Bissau, Senegal, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: KwaZulu-Natal: Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (-28.09, 32.1).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders sampled from the Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011). In the DRC it was collected from caves.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. Protected in the Hluhluwe Nature Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Corronca (2002). Known from both sexes. The females can be distinguished by the shape of the elongated or rhomboidal middle field that is always longer than wide. In the males the shape of the tibial apophysis of the palp is similar to that of *S. radiatus* and *S. annulatus*, but in *S. intricatus* the branches are subequal in length and the tip of the conductor is wider than in *S. annulatus*. Size TL 12 mm.

After Corronca 2002

After Lawrence (1952)

Selenops kruegeri Lawrence, 1940

COMMON NAME: Krugerpark Selenops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Lawrence (1940) from Sabie Reserve in Mpumalanga. Known from seven African countries. In South Africa sampled from four provinces (EOO=194 039 km²; AOO=36 km²; 418-1415 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Angola, Botswana, Namibia, Nigeria, Zimbabwe, Zambia and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Onderstepoort (-25.74, 28.19); Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Roodeplaat Research Station (-25.66, 28.35). **Limpopo:** Dendron (Farm Amsterdam) (-23.37, 29.32); Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Potgietersrus/Mokopane (-24.17, 29). **Mpumalanga:** Lydenburg (-25.09, 30.46); Sabie Sabie Reserve (-25.1, 30.78). **Northern Cape:** Kameeldrift (-29.38, 23.8); Kuruman (-27.46, 23.43).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders sampled from the Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

CONSERVATION THREATS: There are no known threats to the species. It is protected in the Sabie Reserve and Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Last revised by Corronca (2002). Known only from the female but the females of *S. kruegeri* can be distinguished by the shape of the epigynal pockets and the shape of the spermathecae. *S. kruegeri* is easily separated from *S. radiatus* by the colour pattern of opisthosoma. Size TL 12-13 mm (Lawrence (1940).

After Lawrence (1940)

After Corronca (2002)

Selenops lesnei Lessert, 1936

COMMON NAME: Mozambique Selenops Flat Spiders

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Lessert (1936) from Mozambique. Known from seven African countries. In South Africa known from two provinces (EOO=5 503 km²; AOO= 12 km²; 894-1328 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range in Africa, the species is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Eritrea, Mozambique, Zimbabwe, Burundi, Somalia, Rwanda and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo*: Moketsi (-23.36, 30.07); Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04). *Mpumalanga*: Mariepskop (-24.58, 30.87),

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders sampled from the Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. and protected in the Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2019).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Corronca (2002). Known from both sexes. *Selenops lesnei* resembles *S. vigilans*, but the females can be distinguished by the shape of the epigynum (middle field is wider and shorter than in *S. vigilans*) and by the shape of the spermathecae. The males are characterized by the shape of the tibial apophysis and the falciform conductor.

After Corronca (2002)

Selenops ovambicus Lawrence, 1940

COMMON NAME: Ovambicus Selenops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Lawrence (1940) from Namibia. Known from seven African countries. In South Africa known from Limpopo (EOO=4 km²; AOO=4 km²; 418 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range in Africa and is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Botswana, Cameroon, Mozambique, Namibia, Senegal, Sudan and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo*: Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders sampled from the Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. where it is protected in the Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020)

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Corronca (2002). Known from only the female. Carapace reddish brown, cephalic portion a little darker than thoracic portion, defined at its posterior apex by two short blackish stripes, a narrow incomplete blackish stripe in the middle; thoracic portion with some submarginal spots, radiations from the thoracic striae short and ill-defined, the striae itself deeply grooved and blackish; mandibles blackish brown, ocular area dark; abdomen much macerated; femora of anterior legs with 2 distinct blackish bands on their anterior surfaces, these confluent along the under sides; anterior tibiae with 2 black and 2 lighter bands; labium blackish brown, sternum narrowly margined with black. Size TL 13.4 mm (Lawrence 1940) .

Selenops radiatus Latreille, 1819

COMMON NAME: Common Selenops Flat Spiders

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A cosmopolitan species with a very wide global distribution described by Latreille (1819). Introduced into South Africa where it has been recorded from eight provinces (EOO=478 805 km²; AOO=84 km²; 241-2329 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide global geographical range, the species is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Mediterranean, Africa, India, Myanmar, China. In South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Fort Beaufort (-32.78, 26.62). **Free State:** Platberg Nature Reserve (-28.27, 29.2). **Gauteng:** Boksburg (-26.13, 28.15); Centurion (-25.85, 28.16); Pretoria/Tshwane: Meyerspark (-25.74, 28.314), Onderstepoort (-25.74, 28.19); Rietfontein (-25.70, 28.23), Wonderboom Agricultural Holding (-25.74, 28.19); Roodeplaat Research Station (-25.66, 28.35); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36); Tswaing Crater Nature Reserve (-25.42, 28.08); Cullinan (-25.66, 28.51). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Pongola (Farm Vergeval), district Ngotsche (-27.35, 31.61). **Limpopo:** Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Levubu (-23.08, 30.28); Naboomspruit (-24.52, 28.7); Potgietersrus/Mokopane (24.17, 29); Thabazimbi (-24.6, 27.38). **Mpumalanga:** Sabie (-25.1, 30.78); Sabie Sabie Reserve (-25.1, 30.78). **North West:** Geysdorp (-26.52, 25.29); Zeerust (-25.53, 26.08). **Northern Cape:** Kuruman (27.46, 23.43).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal spiders. The species is also commonly found in houses and outbuildings as well as in a wide range of other habitats. Sampled from in Grassland, Savanna and Thicket biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013). Visser (1993a b) suggested that they may play a role in regulating populations of potato tuber moths, cockroaches and silver-fish.

CONSERVATION THREATS: There are no known threats to the species. Protected in five reserves: Platberg Nature Reserve, Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve, Tswaing Crater Nature Reserve, Sabie Sabie Reserve and the Kruger National Park

TAXONOMIC NOTES: A species known from both sexes. Carapace brown with dark striae radiating forwards and sideways from fovea; abdomen above with dark median area; dark mottled brown on sides, a few white speckles among the predominating brown ones; legs grey with femora paler and all legs with distinct white bands.

After Corronca (2002)

Selenops radiatus from Cullinan Photo Peter Webb

Selenops tenebrosus Lawrence, 1940

COMMON NAME: Gravelotte Selenops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described by Lawrence (1940) from Gravelotte in Limpopo. Species also known from Zimbabwe. In South Africa sampled from several localities in Limpopo (EOO=12 571 km²; AOO=20 km²; 418-1341 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range in southern Africa and is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Zimbabwe and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Limpopo: Gravelotte (-23.95, 30.57); Hoedspruit (-24.34, 30.93); Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Louis Trichardt (-23.04, 29.91).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders in the Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. where it is protected in the Kruger National Park and Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Corronca (2002). Known only from the female. Carapace rich dark reddish brown with a conspicuous pattern of markings in addition to the fovea, foveal radiations, and the boundaries of the cephalic area; mandibles reddish black; abdomen almost entirely black above with 1 or 2 pairs of light spots in its anterior half, ventral surface yellow brown, the sides and posterior margin black, spinners almost encircled with black; legs uniformly black, a little lighter towards their bases. Tibiae I and II with 3 pairs of inferior spines, metatarsi I and II with 2 stout pairs of inferior spines. Size TL 23 mm (Lawrence 1940) .

After Lawrence (1940)

After Corronca (2002)

Selenops tenebrosus from Tshipise Photo John Wilkinson

Selenops tonteldoos Corronca, 2005

COMMON NAME: Tonteldoos Selenops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Mpumalanga endemic described by Corronca (2005) from Dullstroom. The species is known only from the type locality (EOO=4 km²; AOO=4 km²; 1999 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Mpumalanga*: Dullstroom Tonteldoos (-25.42, 30.1).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders sampled from the Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are unknown. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the female. Carapace reddish brown; chelicerae dark brown-reddish and legs dark brown with dorsal portion of the femora light brown, terminal portion of all tibiae and metatarsi with whitish hairs. Abdomen pale yellow with a central, longitudinal dark band with lateral branches and lateral dark spots; terminal portion of the opisthosoma with tufts of white hairs. Venter yellowish. Size TL 14.30 mm (Corronca 2005).

After Corronca (2005)

Selenops zuluanus Lawrence, 1940

COMMON NAME: Ingwavuma Selenops Flat Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described by Lawrence (1940) from Ingwavuma in KwaZulu-Natal. Species known from three southern African countries. In South Africa sampled from three provinces including four protected areas (EOO=115 732 km²; AOO=44 km²; 47-1411 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range in southern Africa the species is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Botswana, Zimbabwe and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **KwaZulu-Natal:** uMkuzi Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Zululand Ingwavuma (-28.33, 31.08); Phinda Game Reserve (-27.72, 32.38). **Limpopo:** Kruger National Park (Letaba) (-23.83, 31.58); Kruger National Park (Timbavati) (-24.27, 31.63); Kruger National Park (Shingwedzi) (-23.12, 31.43); Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Potgietersrus/Mokopane (-24.17, 29); Vivo, Farm Bergfontein (-23.04, 29.27); Goro Game Ranch near Vivo (-23.04, 29.27). **Mpumalanga:** Kaapmuiden (-25.54, 31.33).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living cryptozoic nocturnal ground living spiders sampled from the Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. It is protected in uMkuzi Game Reserve, Ndumo Game Reserve, Kruger National Park and Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Corronca (2002). Known from both sexes. Carapace reddish brown, darker anteriorly, with dark marginal border, some ill-defined thoracic striae; indistinct dark stripe bisecting cephalic area; abdomen almost uniformly black, speckled with some minute light dots, those near the anterior margin larger; legs dark anterior surfaces of femora pale remaining segments uniformly black except tarsi which are dark brown. Size TL 12-13 mm (Lawrence 1940).

After Lawrence (1940)

Selenops zuluanus male Photo ASD

Selenops zuluanus male from Phinda Photo Allen Jones

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